

ALFA
UNLOCKING THE BIOGAS POTENTIAL
OF LIVESTOCK FARMING

D1.3

Case studies of livestock farms leading biogas uptake

SIE

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ABBREVIATIONS

CHP	Combined Heat and Power - Cogeneration
CO₂	Carbon Dioxide
EE	Energy Efficiency
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
ESCOs	Energy Service Companies
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GPS	Method for harvesting and using green plants for renewable energy production
PPC	Public Power Corporation
PSR	Piano di Sviluppo Rurale (Rural development plan)
RES	Renewable Energy Source

Executive Summary

The ALFA project focuses on boosting biogas uptake in livestock farms throughout Europe, by studying biogas (and other renewable energy sources) use cases in six nations: Spain, Germany, Belgium, Greece, Denmark, and Slovakia, with the main goal of identifying adoption constraints for biogas technology and how real successful cases have solved these challenges.

This deliverable presents the case studies selected per ALFA hub, with the intention of identifying and analysing at least 3 use cases that are leading the uptake of biogas and biomethane solutions for heating and electricity in each country. A total of 20 cases were studied by the consortium partners.

This report describes the methodology followed, including the definition of the eligibility criteria and other necessary materials, as well as the description of all the use cases studied.

1. Introduction

The activities described in this report are part of WP1, which is the opening package for the ALFA project, with the objective of assessing the biogas market uptake conditions, challenges and developing case studies of biogas solutions in farming, everything in the context of the ALFA regions: Belgium, Denmark, Greece, Italy, Slovakia, and Spain.

This report contains the activities related to *T1.3: Study of real-life successful cases of farms uptake of biogas solutions (M4-M7, February to May 2023)*, including the methodology followed, definition of the eligibility criteria, design of questionnaire for the interviews, and the identification, selection and description of the most promising case studies.

The activities and decisions carried out from M4-M7 in order to fulfil this report's objectives were supported by other WP1 tasks:

- 1) *T1.1 – Analysis of framework conditions influencing the uptake of biogas in the livestock farming industry (M1-M5)*: As support for this and all following tasks, a stakeholder matrix document was created on the project's SharePoint by QPL in order to register all stakeholders approached throughout the project's lifetime and to centralize the information for the whole consortium. Also, via the interviews conducted to biogas stakeholders, a first approach on each country's status regarding the biogas and biomethane market, as well as their challenges and drivers were identified. In this way, the stakeholder matrix provided a starting contact list for finding case studies, and the challenges and drivers identified were used to draft the questionnaire for the successful cases.
- 2) *T1.2 – Identify needs, specificities and (mis)perceptions that drive or hamper biogas market uptake (M1-M6)*: This task gathered very valuable information regarding regional specificities for each country and even the ease (or difficulty) to obtain answers in certain regions somehow also reflects the situation regarding the awareness of the audience and the size of said audience. This task provided extra information in order to validate already identified pain-points and drivers, as well as to pay attention to newly identified factors that could affect the uptake of the technologies.

These 2 tasks have set the landscape for the definition of the methodology of T1.3, as well as the approach to take, taking the lessons learnt from conducting the interviews for T1.1. Since these first three tasks from WP1 overlap in time, the collaboration from all partners (especially from the ALFA hubs) was key in order to use the learnings that were being identified by the moment as this task was developed.

2. Methodology

2.1. Eligibility criteria

In order to study the most promising cases of biogas uptake in each ALFA region, the first task was to define the eligibility and prioritization criteria the consortium would use to rank from more interesting case to less interesting.

For this, a first draft of mandatory eligibility criteria developed by SIE was sent by the end of M3, so the consortium had a base to start the discussion.

A follow-up brainstorming meeting was then organized with all project partners on the beginning of M4, with the intention to complement the 1st draft, while keeping in mind the specific challenges that each ALFA hub had already identified thanks to the interviews from T1.1.

The session was carried using Mural as an interactive platform to allow all partners to include their input in a written form to outline discussions carried via Teams. In the figure below is a screenshot of the session's resulting canvas.

What makes a biogas farmer/promotor/supplier a success case in your opinion?

In Italy: the one that take the opportunity to improve their business thanks to the AD plant	technology provider	plant owner	In Italy: the one that reduced their dependence on fossil fuel costs using RES
In Slovakia - due to the regulation and responsibility we case support the situation of BGP is not enable right now, so many BGP are deciding whether continue operating -> just to stay in the business is a success.	In Italy: the one that maximise the use of heat produced by the CHP	For Belgium, also base conditions + to select: one who overcome citizen opposition/ concerns	For Spain: we don't have many to chose from, so the success case would be one the meets the base conditions
Greece: Livestock farms or biogas plants that use manure to produce biogas. Farmer cooperatives that produce biogas are also a success case	utilisation of biogas plant (gas and waste)	kind of intake/ substrates	

Specific challenges to focus on via the case studies you found out through T1.1 interview (please specify country)?

GR: authorisation process, investment cost	In Italy: a) authorisation process by feedstock availability d) farm dimension --> difficult to finance and not enough measure	GR: Is not profitable investment for 1 farm to implement biogas solution. We need feedstock of scale	Spain: best practices to get authorized, connection to the grid
Slovakia - legislation and difficult & long authorisation process, not efficient state support/	DE: availabilities of construction materials	GR: Legislation	Belgium: authorization (Flanders), financing for big plants, tech reliability for small plants, NIMBY
SK - no willingness of financial institutions and private investors to invest due to the amendments in legislation/instability	GR: NIMBY	GR: Grid is overloaded, very few applications are accepted	Available technologies and know how from professionals

What information should we get from these case studies to help us provide better support services?

Envisioning other project tasks, is there any useful information for you to obtain during this study to complement previous research?

Figure 1: Brainstorming Mural session result

The Mural structure and the lead questions were prepared in advance by SIE, but all partners participated in filling in each of the sticky notes presented above, while discussions carried on during the meeting.

Among the “questions” to answer and the feedback obtained during the session were:

1) What makes a biogas farmer/promotor/supplier a successful case?

This started discussions on what a successful case was for our project’s context, while also trying to identify which stakeholders we could reach out to and what were the minimum requirements to be considered a successful case.

2) Specific challenges identified through the T1.1 interview

This section had each partner enlisting the challenges found until the moment, since T1.1 was still in progress by the time of the session and the findings were not yet formalized in the final report. The idea was to see if there was common ground among all regions and if there was the need to draft specific conditions for some countries.

3) What information do we need from the case studies to help us provide better support services?

This question was aimed with WP2 activities in mind, and the barriers for biogas uptake were discussed more into detail in this section.

4) Envisioning other tasks, is there any useful information we can obtain at this stage?

This question’s objective was to see what subsequent tasks could benefit from the information obtained from the case studies, other than T1.3.

After the session, SIE summarized the discussions and findings, and the final eligibility conditions were decided during M4. These were divided into basic conditions (all 3 must be met by all cases):

- ✓ **The plant or farm must be based in one of the ALFA countries:** Belgium, Denmark, Greece, Italy, Slovakia, and Spain.
- ✓ **The representative of the plant or farm must agree to participate through a consent form and/or in written form, allowing us to use the interview insights and photos.**
- ✓ **Must involve one of the following stakeholders:** Livestock farmers/farmer groups/farmer cooperatives that produce biogas, or biogas plants successfully cooperating with livestock farmers, or livestock farmers/farmer groups/farmer cooperatives using other types of RES. Any biogas plant considered **must use manure as one of their feedstocks.**

And then, a list of extra criteria was provided in case the partners needed to decide among several possibilities (in order of priority):

- 1) **Gender balance:** since there are many male participants until this point in the project, the involvement of women was favoured.
- 2) **Upgrade to biomethane:** the number of biomethane plants is lower than the biogas plants number, so the consortium favoured these in the studies.
- 3) **Use of cutting-edge technology:** the use of state-of-the-art processes, machinery, or techniques (in relation to the innovation level of the region being considered, of course) was favoured.
- 4) **Geographical approach:** If possible, the selection of cases distributed in different regions was favoured.
- 5) **Different approach:** Cases with different and innovative uses of biogas were favoured.
- 6) **Use of different sources of feedstock:** Cases that used manure coming from different sources (cattle, pigs, etc) were favoured.
- 7) **Other RES:** Cases that implemented other RES in livestock farming.

2.2. Development of related materials

During M4 and the first half of M5, SIE worked on and produced all the related materials for the task.

Starting with the transformation of the eligibility criteria into a simple guide for partners to access the information in a simple manner, in the form of a PDF/word document (can find it attached in ANNEX A1).

The following step was to design the questionnaire for the interviews with the successful cases. In parallel to other activities, a first draft of the questionnaire was developed by SIE and then circulated within the consortium. All partners provided their feedback, and the final version was made by gathering all comments and suggestions. The final questionnaire used can be found in ANNEX A2.

Also, the original consent form template created by QPL was modified specifically for the purposes regarding the use of data for T1.3 to ensure this activity stayed compliant with GDPR when collecting the interviewees' data.

Though related discussions during the development of these materials, it became clear that the idea to promote the successful cases was important to leverage the results from the project, and also to

boost communication and dissemination KPIs. SIE, with the collaboration of WR and all partners, also designed a PowerPoint template to serve as part of the promotion materials, including the most interesting information and best practices to showcase the studies. The consortium agreed to release the successful cases as social media materials in order to attract more interest to the project and to also promote the studied successful cases of farms/plants. The PowerPoint template is attached as ANNEX A3.

Finally, in order to ease the partner's work in reporting the information from their interviews, SIE also provided the deliverable template, indicating the sections where the partners were expected to contribute and organise the information gathered from the cases, to ensure the contributions were as homogeneous as possible.

2.3. Screening of successful cases and repository

The definition of the final eligibility conditions allowed the partners to start identifying cases from their networks and also through ALFA the stakeholder matrix. The methodology to follow was to first identify **6 successful cases by ALFA region** with the criteria previously defined and start contacting the 3 most promising ones (considering the prioritization criteria). If there was no response or if they did not provide consent, the partner would engage the following 3. If the last three failed, then the partner would engage new cases but focusing only on the base conditions to maximize the possibilities of engagement.

The screening began on M4 once the eligibility conditions were clear, while the materials were being developed by SIE. The consortium agreed to use the stakeholder matrix to keep track of the contacts engaged for the successful cases. Then, another document was created in order to follow up the status of the case study's contacting, signature of the consent form, and interview.

The repository of case studies was also created in the project's GoogleDrive with the relevant documents for each case, provided by the respective partners.

3. Case studies

In the following pages are the case studies identified by the consortium for each region, including a summary of the information provided by the participants to the ALFA hubs via interview/short meeting and/or questionnaires.

3.1. Belgium

Use case 1: Biomelkveebedrijf Hollevoet (Diksmuide, Belgium)

Description of the plant/farm

Biomelkveebedrijf Hollevoet is located in Diksmuide (Flanders), Belgium, and utilises a biogas plant from BioTechnics. They constructed their plant back in 2012 with a manure bag system from Bioelectric, but later upgraded it in 2017 to a concrete silo type. The farm is relatively small and operates a herd of approximately 115 cows with additional young cattle. Moreover, the installed power of the micro digester is 9.7 kW, with a reactor volume of 256 m³.

In terms of feedstock, the plant exclusively utilises fresh manure from their own cows, which is heated to 38 degrees Celsius using a chauffage boiler, and it can run 22/23 hours a day when the manure is at the appropriate temperature. The biogas produced is solely used for generating electricity, which is sufficient to meet the farm's electricity needs. While gas production has improved significantly since the spring, the exact reasons for this improvement remain unknown. Finally, the biogas plant is owned and managed by the farm owners, specifically the interviewee and his wife, without additional employees needed to operate or maintain the plant.

Investment on the plant

The initial investment for constructing the biogas plant, which served as a pilot project for BioTechnics, amounted to an estimated €140,000 – €150,000, including the pumps and the other peripheral infrastructure. However, according to the interviewee, the current cost of implementing such a plant has probably changed, as there has been a considerable increase in prices. Later, a new engine was installed at a cost of approximately €9000, as the previous engine had already run for 16,000 hours and was no longer functioning optimally.

The implementation of the biogas plant was primarily driven by the desire to mitigate energy costs, with sustainability also serving as a key motivator. Prior to the installation of the current biogas plant, the farm had employed a pocket digester, which eventually broke down. Consequently, a search for a more sustainable and efficient alternative led to the consideration of solar panels, though the idea was deemed infeasible. The biogas plant was ultimately chosen as it didn't require any modifications to the existing infrastructure, making it a more feasible option.

External funding for the implementation of the plant was secured through a one-time subsidy payment of €54,000. The subsidy was integral to cover the maintenance and operational costs of the plant and played a significant role in the decision-making process. Although there was a fair amount of paperwork involved in obtaining the subsidy, BioTechnics offered valuable assistance throughout the process.

Authorization process

The authorization process for the plant was relatively straightforward, with the permit being obtained without any notable issues. The farm was able to submit the application directly, and the authorization was granted in a timely manner. The initial plant was established in 2012, and a permit amendment was necessary in 2017 in order to account for the switch to the new system that uses a concrete silo type.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The selection of technologies for the plant was carried out in close collaboration with BioTechnics. The installation plan was developed with the goal of remaining below 10 kW to avoid the need for modifications to the existing electrical infrastructure. In terms of public reception, the plant has not generated any complaints from nearby residents due to the rural nature of the area, and the plant's good insulation which has prevented any unpleasant odours from emanating. Proper insulation is important, as any detectable odour could be indicative of a gas leak.

Regarding plant maintenance, BioTechnics designed the installation in such a way that the farmers can perform standard maintenance themselves, and they do so every 500 hours. Only in the event of a malfunction or technical problem, they need to call on the technology provider for assistance. Fortunately, as reported by the interviewee, such problems are rare.

End-use of energy

In 2019, virtually all of the annual consumption of the farm, which included two milking robots, was covered by the energy produced by the biogas plant. Currently, the biogas produced by the plant is not upgraded to biomethane.

Overall assessment

Biomelkveebedrijf Hollevoet operates a relatively small biogas plant, compared to the one in Wallonia (use case 2), and uses exclusively manure as a feedstock. The investment for implementing the biogas plant in this case was higher compared to the other case in Flanders (use case 3), and securing partial public financing for the investment was not a complex process due to the assistance provided by the tech provider. Additionally, the authorization process was straightforward without any particular challenge, as it is the case in Heirbaut aLgricuture, which is also based in Flanders. Furthermore, in all of the Belgian cases, there were no objections from locals during the realization. From a technical aspect, the maintenance of the plant is conducted by both the farmer and the company that constructed the plant, contrary to Ferme de la Roche-Madou where the maintenance is solely handled by the company that provided and installed the plant.

The interviewee's advice to fellow farmers looking to install a similar biogas plant would be to consider the daily work and maintenance required, which usually involves 15 minutes per day, but may vary depending on the condition of the system. The maintenance of the engine requires significant time and attention, and it is not advisable to install one if there is no willingness to undertake the necessary efforts. Additionally, regular checking of the manure pumps and water circuit pressure levels are crucial for optimal operation.

In terms of cost recovery, the repayment period for the investment took around 6 to 7 years, as is typical for this type of plant, although it largely depends on the performance of the system. Further, it is important to conduct 4 to 5 analyses of the manure before installation to assess its potential. The quality of fresh manure is a main success factor, and liquid manure is easier to work with than

thick cow manure. For a new system, it is recommended to invest in an unit with solid feeds and a vacuum to facilitate clean-up and collection without requiring additional storage. Additionally, installing a basin for digestate storage directly after the digester can reduce costs.

Use case 2: Ferme de la Roche-Madou (Vierves-sur-Viroin, Belgium)

Description of the plant/farm

The biogas plant of the Ferme de la Roche-Madou is located in Vierves-sur-Viroin, Wallonia, Belgium. The plant was constructed in 2017, with the financial support of EU and Walloon funding. The farm has a size of 145 hectares for grazing and cultivation and 45 cattle. The primary feedstock for the digester process is the manure from the cattle, supplemented with energy crops such as maize and beetroot.

Furthermore, the plant has a capacity of 160kW, with a gas output of 70-90 m^3 of biogas per hour. The plant uses the “infinitely mixed” (“infiniment mélangée” in French) liquid process for the digester. The end-use for the biogas produced is predominantly for the co-generation of heating and electricity, with 95% of the biogas being used for this purpose. The remaining 5% of the biogas is used for the production of biomethane. Lastly, in terms of employment, the farm has a total of 4 full-time male employees and 1 male trainee. Some photos of the Ferme de la Roche-Madou’s farm and biogas plant facilities are presented below.

Figure 2: Ferme de la Roche-Madou farm and livestock

Figure 3: Picture of the Ferme de la Roche-Madou biogas plant and storage unit

Investment on the plant

The implementation of the plant required an upfront investment of approximately €1.5M. The decision to implement the plant was made to diversify the types of agriculture and income streams, as well as to cover labour costs associated with workers on the farm. To assess the feasibility of the project, an external company was hired to conduct a study and assessment.

Obtaining the necessary funding for the implementation of the plant was a significant challenge, due to limited access to finance. To secure financing, the farm contacted an investment fund for assistance in obtaining a bank credit. Additionally, the farm was able to secure subsidies totalling €550,000 from EU funds for agricultural development and from the Walloon region.

Authorization process

The authorization process for the plant was a complex undertaking, requiring the acquisition of urban planning and environmental permits. In order to obtain these permits, a thorough risk assessment was conducted, which together with the feasibility study mentioned above, incurred a cost of €25,000. The process of obtaining the necessary permits and deployment was lengthy, taking a total of two years to complete, including the study, permit, acquisition, and search for financing process. The study and authorization processes were conducted with the assistance of external parties, as it was deemed necessary to secure the expertise required for the task at hand. It is worth noting that the regulatory framework governing the implementation of the plant did not differentiate, at the time, between small and large installations, meaning that the same level of scrutiny and compliance was required regardless of the size of the plant.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The decision to choose the specific technology was based on its suitability for their type of agricultural exploitation and the relative simplicity of the technology. The implementation process was carried out without any issues regarding opposition from local people as the area surrounding the plant is barely urbanised. In terms of maintenance, a German company contracted to install the plant is also responsible for the maintenance.

End-use of energy

The plant uses approximately 30 kW for its own functioning and the rest of the electricity is commercialised. The 5% of biogas that is upgraded to biomethane is used as fuel for vehicles, and the heat from biogas is utilised for drying local wood. In terms of revenue generated from using biogas and other types of renewable energy, the plant generates about €150,000 to €200,000 annually, which is used to cover the costs of agricultural activities, salaries, and other expenses.

Overall assessment

L'unité de biométhanisation de la Ferme de la Roche-Madou operates a larger biogas plant compared to the other two cases and uses energy crops apart from manure. The investment for implementing the biogas plant in this case was very high compared to the other two cases, and obtaining the necessary funding for the implementation of the plant was a significant challenge due to limited access to finance. In contrast to the use cases based in Flanders, this case encountered a longer, costlier and more complex authorisation and assessment process. This could be partially attributed to the large size of the plant and the investment required. Additionally, it should be noted that the interviewee also mentioned that the process for obtaining permits in Wallonia is the same for small and large installations. This differs from the findings of our desk research for T1.1, where we identified two different types of permits depending on the scale of the plant, indicating that the current situation may differ from our earlier findings [1]. Lastly, in terms of maintenance of the plant, this is solely handled by the construction company contrary to Biomelkveebedrijf Hollevoet and Heirbaut aLgriciculture where the maintenance is partially a responsibility of both the farmers and the technology provider.

According to the interviewee, installing a similar biogas is due to various factors such as the high cost of organic matter, access to finance, and sizing the plant appropriately. The success factors include prioritising the use of animal waste and maximising the amount of waste that can be used without extra processing. It is also essential to assess the amount of energy that can be injected into the grid for co-generation and how much to upgrade. Additionally, transporting manure from far away locations is complex and expensive, therefore it is recommended to use a significant amount of manure generated from one's own farm. Furthermore, while assistance from various organisations is available to simplify the process, dealing with regulatory requirements can still be challenging. To facilitate the replication of the biogas plant, it is recommended to simplify regional regulations and address regional issues related to the distribution of the manure.

Use case 3: Heirbaut aLgriciculture (Temse, Belgium)

Heirbaut aLgriciculture operates a Bioelectric (technology provider) biogas installation, specifically a "pocket digester", in Temse (Flanders), Belgium, which was constructed in 2012 in an effort of the farm owner to utilise the manure in an innovative way. The farm has 65 cows and 65 hectares of cultivated land for cereals, grasses, and other crops. Additionally, the biogas plant has a capacity of 10 kW, and produces 5-10 m³/hour of biogas, which amounts to at least 40,000 m³ per year. In 2017, the anaerobic digester was replaced with a more modern plant of the same capacity, provided by Bioelectric.

The plant uses only manure from their own cows, which is collected from a small pit that keeps it fresh before putting it into the digester. The interviewee highlighted the importance of having a suitable stable with an appropriate floor system to keep the manure fresh before inserting it into the

digester. Lastly, in terms of employment, only the owner and his wife work at the plant, while additional personnel may be needed when the digestate is used for fertilising the fields.

Some photos showcasing the biogas plant and the farm's facilities are provided in the following figures.

Figure 4: Bioelectric biogas plant at Heirbaut aLgriculture farm

Figure 5: Picture of Heirbaut aLgriculture farm and livestock

Investment on the plant

The investment process for the implementation of the biogas plant at Heirbaut aLgriculture farm was initiated in 2012 with an upfront investment of €90,000. In 2017, the anaerobic digester needed to be replaced, and the cost of the new plant was between €90,000 – €100,000, half of which was covered by Bioelectric, the technology provider, since it was part of a research activity to pilot their new technology. The decision to invest was motivated not only by financial considerations, but also by the desire to reduce their environmental impact by improving manure processing and reducing ammonia/nitrogen and methane emissions.

Furthermore, the company used evaluation methods provided by Bioelectric to calculate the financial outcome based on different parameters and assumptions. Funding for the implementation was

obtained through a bank loan, and the process went smoothly without any issues. Similarly, obtaining the necessary construction permit went also smoothly.

Authorization process

The construction permit for their Bioelectric “pocket digester” biogas installation was obtained directly from the municipality, as the size of their installation (10 kW) did not require an impact study or an environmental permit. However, if the plant was larger (e.g. 20 kW), they would have needed an impact study and an environmental permit.

The authorisation process was taken care of by the company itself and did not face any challenges. In 2017, when they replaced the entire installation with a more modern plant of the same capacity, a renewed permit was not required as the capacity of the plant remained the same.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The implementation of the plant involved the installation of the digester by the manufacturing company. The technologies implemented were selected based on the evaluation methods provided by the biogas plant company, which allowed for calculation of financial outcomes and consideration of environmental impact. In terms of citizen opposition, there were no particular objections from the locals during the implementation process.

In terms of maintenance, technical issues requiring the use of machinery are addressed by the biogas plant company, while regular maintenance, such as replacing filters and oil, are the responsibility of the farmer.

End-use of energy

The plant generates electricity, which covers up to 65% of their business needs, including pasteurising and freezing milk in their dairy products facility. The remaining energy is planned to be covered by photovoltaic installations to be installed in the future.

In terms of upgrade, the biogas is not upgraded to biomethane, but the farmer has considered the possibility of isolating CO₂ and providing it directly to the algae they cultivate to produce pure biomethane. However, upgrading to biomethane is not currently feasible due to the size of the installation. Some of the CO₂ released during the biogas production is already partially used to grow micro-algae chlorella. The exhaust gas CO₂ can only be utilised for algae cultivation during the day, when the plants are undergoing photosynthesis.

Overall assessment

Heirbaut aLgricuture operates a pocket digester exclusively fed with manure, similarly to Biemelkveebedrijf Hollevoet. The investment for the implementation of the biogas plant in this scenario was smaller compared to those from Biemelkveebedrijf Hollevoet and Ferme de la Roche-Madou, whereas obtaining financing for the project was not a complicated process. It should be noted though, that the plant in this case and in Biemelkveebedrijf Hollevoet were constructed prior to the current regulatory issues related to the permits for biogas plant construction, which are on hold in Flanders, as reported in the context of T1.1 [1]. Furthermore, similarly, to use Biemelkveebedrijf Hollevoet (use case 1) which is also based in Flanders, the authorisation process was not complicated and did not pose any significant challenges. Moreover, the maintenance of the

plant is carried out by both the farmer and the construction company that built the plant, in contrast to Ferme de la Roche-Madou (use case 2).

According, to the interviewee, the feasibility of deploying a plant can be limited due to the high costs involved in feeding the cows, which is necessary for quality manure production. Additionally, significant investments are required. Further, the farmer highlighted the fact that a small-scale biogas plant requires the manure of approximately 70 cows, and it less profitable than larger-scale plants. However, obtaining permits for upscaling can be challenging, due to environmental concerns, such as nitrogen emissions, and local authorities' resistance to farms growing in terms of livestock numbers.

Additionally, the farmer appears to have taken an innovative approach to utilising the manure and exploring ways to reduce environmental costs, which could be seen as a state-of-the-art approach.

Overall, factors such as the availability of resources and regulations in different regions may impact the feasibility of implementing a similar plant.

3.2. Denmark

Use case 1: Brdr. Thorsen Biogas (Nimtofte, Denmark)

Description of the plant/farm

Thorsen has a self-operating farm and a biogas plant, with around 120 ha. They mainly farm pigs, with a production of 24,000 pcs, and sows (around 650 pcs).

The biogas plant is fed with approximately 100 tons of biomass per day, which corresponds to around 36,500 tons per year. The biomass consists of slurry, deep litter, silage straw, silage grass and glycerine. The solid biomass amounts to approx. 17-20 tons per day and the glycerin makes up approx. 3 tons per day, while the rest is manure.

The plant is equipped with 2,375 kW engines with an electrical efficiency of 38.5%.

below are some pictures of the farm and plant.

Figure 6: Owner and manager of the biogas plant Steffen Thorsen

Figure 7: Picture of the biogas plant

Figure 8: Two MAN engines installed at the biogas plant

The plant consists of 3 biogas reactors of a total of 16,000 m³, a Vogelsang Premix solids intake, Xergi SRO plant, pumps, sulfur filter, gas storage and 2 MAN V12 gas engines which provide a total of 1800 kW electricity and heat.

The technology was originally a standard from the turnkey contractor, based on receiving slurry and glycerin. The plant has since been expanded with options for feeding solid biomass and for the mechanical pre-treatment of the biomass.

With the experience they have gained, Thorsen has a well-functioning plant that they can look after and maintain themselves: the operation of the plant himself, with feeding, monitoring and optimization take an effort of approx. 2-3 hours per day.

The facility is maintained as needed by staff from one of the other companies that Thorsen owns. This concerns the maintenance of pumps and other mechanical matters.

Investment on the plant

From their start in 2000, approximately €2M was invested in the facility. Since then, the facility has been rebuilt and upgraded in a few rounds, most recently in 2018 with an extra reactor tank. The financing was obtained via a bank loan.

Authorization process

Thorsen cannot recall the challenges in connection with the first establishment of the facility, but regarding some of the later conversions and extensions there have been many challenges with a slow and difficult case processing. One of the ways to overcome this administrative difficulties has been to contact the mayor of the municipality directly, who called a joint meeting, after which progress was made in the case.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

Steffen Thorsen spends around 2-3 hours a day to operate the biogas plant. In addition, help is “outsourced” for maintenance tasks from one of Brødrene Thorsensn's other companies. Brdr. Thorsen consists of 5 different companies and employs a total of 110 employees.

End-use of energy

The gas is used in the gas engines after purification from sulphur, producing a total of 1.6M m³ of methane per year.

The cooling water from the engines is used for process heat and heating of stables as well as district heating. Indeed, approximately 40-50% of the heat consumption in the entire Nimtofte city district heating, that currently delivering heat for 405 households, is provided by the cooling system of the 2 engines of the plant.

Overall assessment

In Denmark it is usually good business to run biogas plants, so the family would do it again.

Regarding implementation, it is necessary to have good advice both on the technical side and on the official process when establishing a plant, and one of the most important factors is securing the biomass base.

Right now, they are participating in the planning of a much larger biogas plant, which must be able to handle 800,000 tonnes of biomass per year. As they are in a place where it is not possible to connect to the gas grid, they plan to upgrade the gas to both liquid methane and carbon dioxide, and they hope to get started with the establishment within the next few years.

Use case 2: Madsen Bioenergi (Spøttrup, Denmark)

Description of the plant/farm

Madsen Bioenergi is owned by 3 brothers: Kim Madsen, Boe Madsen and Per Madsen. Together, the brothers farm 450 ha of arable land, where they grow corn, grass, seed grain and seed grass for harvest.

Figure 9: Boe Madsen owns Madsens Bioenergi together with his two brothers

Figure 10: The biogas plant is made in concrete tanks with a soft top.

Figure 11: The biogas is upgraded to biomethane in an amine scrubber plant.

The upgraded biogas produced in their farm is distributed via the gas grid. In order to upgrade 1200 m³ of biogas with 33% CO₂ with an amine scrubber, around 800 kW are needed. The heat is provided by a straw boiler, which is in the straw house (1500 m²), which contains a boiler room and space for big bales and wood chips. Specifically, a 950-kW hot water biomass boiler from Linka and a gas boiler for back-up are installed in this room.

The daily operation and maintenance of the biogas plant is handled by Kim, Boe, Per and one employee. The biogas plant is designed to mainly process livestock manure, including deep bedding. The plant is also fed with energy crops such as maize and grass and residual products from industry.

Madsen Bioenergi is one of the first biogas plants in Denmark that upgrades the biogas to biomethane and sends it out into the gas network on a full scale.

Since the Madsen brothers do not have livestock themselves, they get all manure and bedding from outside, by putting contracts in place with the region's farmers to provide the feedstock. They treat around 140,000 tonnes of manure per year and in addition 30,000 tonnes of other types of biomasses.

Investment on the plant

The initial investment was €8.7M including the investment in the upgrade facility. In addition to that, an EU grant of €1.5M was given to the facility, and also the gas company HMN helped finance the upgrade facility. The rest was financed via the Danish Growth Fund and also a bank loan.

Authorization process

The brothers and one of their wives have themselves been responsible for all the proceedings in connection with the establishment of the facility. They received help with part of the environmental case processing from the company Lundsby. The municipality was very helpful throughout the process.

There was a very extensive case processing in connection with the establishment of a biogas plant and it takes a long time.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The Madsen brothers obtained two competing offers for the delivery of the plant in the form of a turnkey contract. The establishment of buildings was tendered to local craftsmen.

From the start, residents and all interested parties were involved in the planning, among other things, citizen meetings were held where everyone could come. There have been no complaints or objections to the biogas plant. The three brothers carry out all the operations and maintenance of the plant themselves.

End-use of energy

All the biogas is sold via the gas network. The necessary heat for the upgrading process and the operation of the facility is provided by burning straw.

Overall assessment

The three brothers are all farmers but have no livestock themselves. All manure and deep bedding is obtained by agreement with neighbours. As one of the first, they installed an upgrading that turned the biogas into biomethane, which is sold via the gas network. They consider that implementing a biogas plant is good business.

Use case 3: I/S Kuhr Hedegaard (Rødkærsbro, Denmark)

Description of the plant/farm

Henry Kuhr is a farmer with 700 dairy cows and bred. Pig production has been shut down but can be resumed if conditions improve, they had a capacity of breeding 6,000 pigs.

Henry and his sons have 4 different properties, but milking is only done at Kuhr-Hedegaard, where the biogas plant is situated. The areas are cultivated with:

- 400 ha with maize
- 170 ha with grass
- 50 ha with canola
- 80-100 ha with wheat

The biogas plant was built in 2016-2017. The facility was developed in two stages and is currently being expanded with an additional storage tank. The feedstock used for the biogas plant include manure and the deep bedding from the farm's four properties, accounting for around 100 m³/day of slurry and 13-15 tons/day of deep bedding.

In addition to their own manure and biomass, the facility receives some biomass from external suppliers, including (per week):

- 50 tons of cheese
- 75 tons of soap
- Flour
- 1-2 drags of glycerin

- Whey from Arla's dairy

Figure 12: Henry Kuhr owner and manager of the biogas plant

Figure 13: Receiving tanks and reactor tanks at the biogas plant

Figure 14: A significant part of the biomass used is deep bedding and silage grass

The facility consists of two bioreactors in steel tanks and two reactors in concrete tanks. In addition, they also have two storage tanks. The biomass used as feedstock is mixed in a mixing tank once a day, from where it is pumped to the first two bioreactors. The total volume of the reactor tanks is approx. 23000 m³, and the decay temperature is set to 46-47 degrees.

The resulting digestate is used in their own farms and a portion is also allocated to neighbours with plant cultivation.

Investment on the plant

From the start, it was very difficult to get the financing secured, as it required very extensive documentation. In the end, the Growth Fund provided loans, but with a very high interest rate. During the last expansion of the facility, money was borrowed from a pool for green investments in the credit union Nykredit with a favourable interest rate of 0%.

The establishment of the biogas plant, gas line to the dairy and storage facilities cost €3.6M, and the expansion of the second stage cost €1.3M.

Gas prices fluctuate a lot, but the payback period is less than 10 years.

Authorization process

The establishment of the biogas plant took approximately 1 year and they had an external consultant to help them. They carried out the expansion in the second stage themselves. It went really well, and the municipality was benevolent. For smaller farm biogas plants, the application procedure is affordable, but for larger joint biogas plants, the process is more difficult.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

After an inspection of several plants, it was chosen to use the technology proposed by Combigas, and the plant was purchased as a turn-key delivery from said company.

At the beginning, they had the pumping company Landia come and service their pumps, but they have now learned to change spare parts themselves, which is significantly cheaper. The daily operation and feeding of the biomass are carried out by Henry himself.

A total of 15 people work at the farms and biogas plant, 14 male and 1 female.

End-use of energy

Biogas production has fluctuated a lot, when it has been at its worst it has been down to 300m³/hour, while in their best period it has been up to 900 m³/hour, with an average of 700 m³ per hour. The methane percentage has been low, around 55%, but has risen to more than 60% in some periods, and now has stabilised at 57-58%.

The gas is delivered through a gas line to Arla's dairy, where the gas is used in a CHP installation (three engines). The heat is allocated by the dairy and if there is more heat than the dairy itself can use, it is allocated to the local district heating supply.

Overall assessment

The biogas plant is a major asset for the operation. This farm has one of the few plants that sell biogas to a large dairy company which uses it in an engine installation. The power is sold to the electricity grid and heat is used partly at the dairy farm and partly for district heating supply of homes in the city.

3.3. Greece

Use case 1: Biogas Lagada S.A. (Kolchiko, Greece)

Description of the plant

Biogas Lagada S.A. is located in plot 667, in Kolchiko of the regional unit of Thessaloniki, in North Greece, and it was constructed in 2016. The biogas unit has a nominal capacity of 1MW and produces 12,000m³ of biogas daily. The unit employs five people, all males.

In terms of processes, the raw materials are transported by suitable vehicles to the plant, where they are stored. Then, they are fed on a twenty-four-hour basis into the production process, which consists of a primary and a secondary digester. The biogas produced is collected and used in a co-generation unit for electricity and heat production, while the digestate is pasteurized and is used as a soil conditioner. The figure below Figure 15: Unit Overview, Biogas Lagada S.A. shows the unit overview.

Figure 15: Unit Overview, Biogas Lagada S.A.

The raw materials are transported either by tanker trucks (for liquid raw materials) and stored in a tank for liquid raw materials (pre-tanker) or by trucks (for dry raw materials) and stored in open storage areas (silage track or biomass storage area). The pre – tank (for liquid raw materials) is an underground tank with a capacity of 300m³, where the liquid is stored and homogenised using agitators.

The solid raw materials, with the help of a telescopic loader, are fed into the solid raw material pre-treatment and feeding system before being transported to the primary digestion tank. The raw materials (both liquid and dry) are fed automatically into the production process on an hourly basis and according to the feed schedule, from the pre-tank (for the liquid) and from the pre-treatment and feeding system for the dry raw materials. The process starts with the primary digester, with a capacity of 4.000m³, where the biomass remains for 30-35 days under continuous stirring and at a temperature of 44°C, producing 60-65% of biogas content. The materials are then fed into the secondary digester also with a capacity of 4.000m³ where they remain for another 60 days, yielding the remaining 35-40% of the biogas. The digested residue from the secondary digester, after 30 days, is transferred to pasteurization tanks where it remains for one hour at 70°C in order to eliminate any pathogens and weed spores and then transferred to the two storage tanks where it is kept about 120 days before being used as a soil fertilizer for crops. Based on the aforementioned, the technology used for biogas production is anaerobic digestion.

Figure 16: Stages of the biogas production processes.

The raw materials are liquid and dry cattle manure, liquid and dry poultry manure, liquid pig manure, whey, liquid mill waste, fruit peel and pulp, fruit and vegetables, silage from energy crops, hatchery waste, grape marc, vinasse, brewer's yeast, aromatic plant distillation residues and by-products of biofuel production.

Investment on the plant

The initial investment was around €4M, and the initial idea was conceived after visiting biogas production plants abroad. A market analysis was initially carried out by the consulting group named ERGOPLANNING, to which the unit belongs, in order to investigate the potential and the capabilities of the area and the risk of such an investment. The acquisition of the funds came from bank financing, in cooperation with Piraeus Bank and finally through the JESSICA Community Initiative [2], the needed funding for the project was secured.

Authorization process

The authorisation process began with a submission of an application to the Department of Veterinary Public Health and then the Environmental Permit for the project was approved, while this step of the authorisation lasted from 6 months to a year. The main difficulties during the licensing were the absence of a legislative framework and insufficient expertise from veterinary service, but the challenges were faced in cooperation with the consulting company ERGOPLANNING, which assisted the whole project.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The implementation of the project started in March of 2016, after the funding of the project was secured. The project was completed in October of the same year, so the implementation phase lasted about 6 months, and went straight into production. The technologies were chosen during on-site visits to exhibitions and biogas plants in European countries such as Italy and Germany. It is important to highlight that no problems were encountered with the local society during the construction of the plant.

The unit is maintained by trained staff and continuous checks, in cooperation with consultants from abroad. A technical team from Austria was responsible for the technical study, and a technical team from Italy was the technical provider. In the beginning of the plant, there were no trained local professionals/technicians, but the employees were trained in order to acquire the needed knowledge and know-how for the maintenance.

The unit ensures the continued feedstock availability, by stable and long-term partnership with farmers, in order to assure the needed amounts of raw materials (cow-dung, etc.). In addition, some farmers are also shareholders of the company to whom the solid and liquid digestate is returned to.

End-use of energy

As mentioned previously, the plant produces 12,000m³ of biogas daily, which is used as input for a co-generation engine to generate electricity, which is sold 100% to the Public Power Corporation (PPC), and heat, which is used for the in-house needs of the plant. Because biomethane is not commercialized in Greece yet, there is an installation of corresponding technology for the conversion of biogas into biomethane, but only in the context of research and development.

After the digestion process, the produced biogas is piped to the dehumidification and desulfurization complex and then is fed to the co-generation engine, which generates electricity (998 kW), which is injected to the grid, as well as heat (1064kW) in the form of hot water at 95°C, which is used in the plant's operation. The figure below shows the co-generation engine.

Figure 17: Co-generation Engine

Overall assessment

According to the interviewee the construction of a biogas plant is a high-risk investment, as it requires a high start-up capital. However, it relies heavily on the circular economy as suppliers of raw materials exploit the solid and liquid digestate as a soil conditioner for the use in their crops.

The success in this biogas plant is accomplished in cooperation with the QLAB analytical laboratory, which systematically implements a sampling plan, monitoring critical physiochemical parameters and ensuring the proper operation of the plant. In addition, Biogas Lagada S.A. participated in many

research projects, both at European and national levels, thus achieving the direct application of innovative technologies, such as photocatalysis.

Use case 2: BIOENERGY NIGRITAS S.A. (Visalia, Greece)

Description of the plant

The second Greek case is named Bioenergy Nigrita S.A., is located in Visalia of the regional unit of Serres, in North Greece and was constructed in 2016. The biogas unit has a nominal capacity of 1MW (an extension up to 3MW is foreseen in the next years) and produces 12,000 m³ of biogas daily. The unit employs ten males. The technology which is used for biogas production is anaerobic digestion, using a digester with a capacity of 4000 m³ at 40-42°C. For the operation of the plant, agricultural products (such as corn silage, grain silage – legumes), livestock waste and agro-industrial residues are used (the supply of solid is carried out separately from the supply of liquids), and using anaerobic digestion process, a CHP engine produces 998 kW of electricity and 1064 kW of heat. The figure below shows an overview of the plant.

Figure 18: BIOENERGY NIGRITAS S.A overview 1

The BIOENERGY NIGRITAS S.A. exploits mainly wastewater of animal origin, wastewater from cheese dairies, olive mills and agricultural products to produce biogas which is used for the generation of electricity after combustion. The raw materials are collected by farmers with whom an agreement has been conducted for a long-term cooperation with the ultimate goal of securing a stable and long-term raw material feedstock supply.

In addition, 75 ton of organic soil conditioner is produced daily, which is an excellent fertilizer for agricultural crops.

Figure 20: BIOENERGZ NIGRITAS S.A overview 2

Authorization process

For the licencing of the plant, an application was first submitted to the Department of Veterinary Public Health and then the Environmental Permit for the project was approved, which are the same processes also for the Biogas Lagada S.A. These processes lasted about 6 months to 1 year. The authorisation process was supported by the consulting company ERGOPLANNING.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The maintenance of the unit is achieved through continuous monitoring and training, in cooperation with the consulting company ERGOPLANNING.

End-use of energy

The end use of energy is electricity generation, which is provided 100% to PPC (Public Power Corporation), while there is the possibility of installing biogas to biomethane upgrading technology under the framework of the research programmes, as there is no legal framework at the moment.

Figure 21: Stages of the production processes

Overall assessment

The interviewee highlighted that investing in a biogas plant is quite important as it ensures the treatment of waste from various sources. The economic viability of such a plant is based firstly on the fact that such plants treat raw material (agricultural and livestock waste, organic fraction of waste, etc.) which often has a zero or negative value and secondary that the products of the plant have an undeniable commercial value. In addition, the participation in research projects is a success factor as this drives the acquisition of deep understanding, knowledge, and expertise.

Use case 3: Lithaios Energeiaki S.A. (Kefalovriso, Greece)

Description of the plant

Lithaios Energeiaki S.A., is based in Kefalovriso, belonging to the regional unit of Trikala, in Central Greece, and it was constructed in 2022. The biogas unit has a nominal capacity of 3MW and produces 36.000m³ of biogas daily. The unit employs six people, all males. The figure below shows an overview of the plant.

Figure 22: Lithaios Energeiaki S.A. Overview

The solid raw materials are transported to the plant and stored in 5 open storage areas (silage trays), while the liquids transported to the plant are stored in an underground tank with stirring technology. The liquids are then pumped through pumps, and the solids are fed in an hourly basis into the first stage of anaerobic digestion process. This stage consists of two anaerobic digestion tanks. The first stage then feeds the second stage, which consists of one anaerobic digestion tank. The biogas collected from the two stages after purification is fed into two internal combustion engines for electricity and heat production. The type of feedstock and the amount on a daily basis was:

- Silages (approx. 90 ton/day)
- Poultry manure (approx. 30 ton/day)
- Cow dung (approx. 40 ton/day)
- Dairy by-products (20 ton/day)

The unit is designed for a high solid's concentration up to 12-13%, compared to other units designed for solids concentrations up to 8-9% during the anaerobic digestion.

Figure 23: Silage Tracks of Lithaios Energeiaki S.A.

Investment on the plant

The initial investment amounted up to €10M, while the funds came from bank financing. The decision to implement the plant was taken after an analysis of the market in the region by PK Energy, in terms of the qualitative and quantitative characteristics of the raw materials and the potential of agreements with local suppliers.

Authorization process

In this use case, the permitting process was the most time-consuming, although the steps were similar to the two previous use cases. There were two main reasons for this delay, (i) the licence was transferred to another owner and (ii) there was strong resistance to the construction from the local community. But this phenomenon has now been solved, during the operation of the plant, as the local society understands the advantages of such a unit. The whole process was assisted by the PK ENERGY company, which designed and constructed the unit.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The implementation of the plant was completed by PK ENERGY, who also selected the technologies which are used in the unit, as a technical company. The maintenance is done by the employees of the plant, while the machines are maintained by their technology supplier.

Figure 24: Lithaios Energeiaki S.A Bioagas Plant

End-use of energy

A hundred percent of the produced electricity is provided to PPC (Public Power Corporation) and injected into the electricity grid, while part of the heat produced is used for own use in the plant. At the moment there are no plans for biogas upgrading into biomethane.

Overall assessment

The interviewee stated during the discussion that such an investment is of low risk, but subject to conditions such as proper initial design, proper operation, and maintenance of the plant, as well as the quality of the raw materials and their management.

As already mentioned, a success factor and what stands out in this particular unit is the high solids concentration in the production process, which differs from other similar plants.

3.4. Italy

Use case 1: La Falchetta Farm (Turin, Italy)

Description of the farm and plant

“La Falchetta” farm, located in Druento (Turin) in the Northern Italian Region of Piedmont, was founded in 1977 inside the natural Park “La Mandria”. Since November 2010, by the will of its owner, Dr. Riccardo Ferrero, La Falchetta has implemented its own Biogas Cogeneration Plant, which was the first in the country to be managed independently. To date, it is still the only Italian plant to comply with the environmental impact assessment (VIE). Furthermore, La Falchetta is a member of the CIB – Italian Biogas Consortium.

The farm, which extends over 2 square kilometres, has been operating in the circular economy since 2010, so the biogas plant was built tailored for the company, not vice versa. The company's production is sufficient to manage the farm (cereals and woody crops in forestry), breeding (beef cattle) and the biogas plant (animal manure becomes biogas but also digestate to fertilise the fields).

La Falchetta has agreements with nearby farmers for the withdrawal of zootechnical manure, and in addition, whenever they find more competitive by-products on the market than theirs, they use them; for example, at the moment we can cite the example of the wheat rumen of slaughterhouses and unsold fruit.

Figure 25 - La Falchetta Biogas Cogeneration Plant

La Falchetta Biogas Cogeneration Plant, which produces 7,200 cubic metres of biogas per day, uses a mesophilic anaerobic process. There are 3 digesters, with a closed tank, of a total of 6,300 cubic metres. To date, biogas generates electricity, after which, as a derivation of the processing of this production, the cogeneration engine creates hot water, also intended for central heating. La Falchetta is also thinking of upgrading to biomethane.

Figure 26: BioEnergy Fair award by Legambiente to La Falchetta

La Falchetta has received the following awards: Bio-Energy Fair from Legambiente as the best plant for environmental management best practices, Ronchi Sustainable Development Foundation as a company in the energy sector, AGRICOLTURA 100 from Confagricoltura and Reale Mutua for land management and improvement of sustainability.

Investment on the plant

The financing for the investment, equal to the approximate figure of €3.5M, was obtained through a direct loan from a bank and an incentive from a public body for agricultural development (ISA – Istituto Sviluppo Agricolo), issued to a consortium of farms of which La Falchetta was a member.

Authorization process

The authorization process lasted about 3 years and a half, and it was made difficult by the location inside a natural park and by the fact that, back in 2010, there was a lack of standardisation for the process. The difficulties were overcome by carefully studying the authorization process, coordinating with the CIB (Italian Biogas Consortium) and making use of the advice of an engineer who had already supervised biogas plant implementations in other European countries.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The construction process of the plant lasted 10 months, with a consultant for the engineering aspects, Eng. Marino of 4u Engineering of Turin, while the market studies were carried out in-house. There were no problems with the citizens as the plant is far from inhabited centres.

There are three employees on the farm, and one of them basically works in the plant, helped by two colleagues at peak times. The management of the plant, therefore, is perfectly integrated with that of the rest of the farm.

As regards the maintenance of the system, the managers of La Falchetta choose to opt for a direct scheduled maintenance on their part, while the maintenance of the engine part is contracted out to an external company (AB Energy of Orzinoi in the province of Brescia, present on all the Italian territory). As for the biomass dissection part, they use other companies, such as DODA Company from Mantova, in Lombardy Region, Northern Italy.

End-use of energy

The biogas produced is converted into electricity and sold to the grid, after deducting the legal self-consumption (about 11% needed by the plant itself). 50% of the entire farm's budget comes from the sale of biogas.

Overall assessment

The case study La Falchetta shows how, according to its owner, Dr. Riccardo Ferrero, the main success factor is the perfect integration of the biogas plant into the farm, in a circular economy system.

Nevertheless, Dr. Ferrero considers the investment for biogas profitable but high-risk because there are variables that are independent of the entrepreneur's management, for example data

transmission problems with energy managers, and the bureaucratic administrative political machine does not work properly (indeed, the situation has worsened since 2010).

For example, when La Falchetta managers decided to implement a biogas plant, in 2010, they started their activity with renewable energy sources proving that the aforementioned plant was connected to their inner agricultural activity, in the sense that the biogas plant operated entirely with the products of the farm.

Therefore, back then, the plant was rightfully and more conveniently taxed as a part of an agricultural company (which had biogas as a connected activity). Unfortunately, all of a sudden in 2014 the new Italian government imposed a new retroactive taxation, upsetting all the business plans made, an inconvenient and absurd change, according to the interviewee, that is sadly a very frequent *modus operandi* in Italy.

As a consequence, even if La Falchetta has received the authorization to build a photovoltaic solar park, it will not implement it because the owner, Dr. Ferrero, has no trust in the Italian legislative administrative system.

La Falchetta is a very representative case study for what concerns the situation of livestock farms that have biogas plants in Northern Italy, where the Piedmont Region is located. Piedmont Region, a predominantly mountainous area that presents the typical continental climate of Northern Italy, is one of the richest areas in Italy, and, generally speaking, economic conditions are more favourable for what concerns technological innovation than other regions in the Centre or the South.

Use case 2 - Trionfi Honorati Farm (Ancona, Italy)

Description of the farm and its plant

Since 1939, the Trionfi Honorati family has managed this farm which is one of the flagships of the Jesi area (Ancona), in the Marche Region of Central Italy. Starting from the early 2000s, Antonio began to take a direct interest in management by introducing great attention to the issues of circularity and sustainability. In 2010, Trionfi Honorati Farm implemented its own Biogas Co-Generation Plant.

On average, there are 160 cows and 200 buffaloes in the farm, for a total of about 360 heads. 1.8 square kilometres of land are used for the cultivation of forage for the animals, while another 0.25 are used for the production on 2 rotations per year of vegetables to be shredded (e.g., corn, triticale, sorghum) to feed the digester. Some interesting examples of sustainable activities are the recovery of traditional crops to produce natural pigments and the reintroduction of hemp for fabrics. With hemp, pilot projects have also been launched for the use of fibres in construction, including the creation of a demonstration house.

Figure 27: Trionfi Honorati stables and photovoltaic panels

The Trionfi Honorati Biogas Cogeneration Plant was the first small/medium sized plant in the Marche region. The anaerobic digester is connected to a co-generator with a nominal power of 249kW. The stables have a system of drains and pumps to automatically collect the sewage and send it to the digester. The manure is also collected semi-automatically and sent to a hopper which loads the digester at regular intervals.

Figure 28: Trionfi Honorati Biogas Cogeneration Plant

Overall, 10 cubic metres of sewage, 12 tons of manure and 3 or 4 tons of shredded wood are used every day. In addition to the biogas plant, in 2010 the Trionfi Honorati family built a 190kW peak photovoltaic system on the stable roofs, which can generate all the electricity needed to the company and transfers the excess energy to the grid.

In the past, by-products from neighbouring farms were also used: olive droppings and pomace which have a high yield even if they entail burdens in terms of management and maintenance. Considering, among other factors, the increase in the costs of these materials, it was decided not to use them anymore and to replace them with self-produced shredded.

The Trionfi Honorati Plant has a good level of automation and furthermore the input materials come entirely from the company. The digestate is spread over the fields. The staff already present in the company, made up of 4 men and 4 women, in addition to the owner, Dr. Antonio Trionfi Honorati, architect and entrepreneur, is therefore sufficient for the management of the plant.

Investment on the plant

The company has benefited from a non-repayable regional loan called PSR of €200,000; the rest was obtained through a bank loan.

The construction of the plant required a total investment of around €1.1M (850,000 for the technological plant + 250,000 for building works, electrical substation, tubs, pipes, and excavations).

The driving factor for the choice was the need to integrate agricultural income. The owner, Dr. Antonio Trionfi Honorati, tried to maintain the basic characteristics of the farm (vocation for cattle breeding and dairy production) and wondered if waste and by-products could become a resource.

In 2008, Dr. Trionfi Honorati became aware of the possibility of producing biogas and began to inquire about sector magazines; subsequently, to better evaluate the investment, he visited some plants already built in northern Italy and in Germany. After the construction of the plant, he was also able to ascertain that the digestate is an excellent soil improver, in some respects even better than animal manure.

Authorization process

The process was quick: just 2 months passed from submitting the application to obtaining the authorization. Most of the process was followed directly by the owner Antonio who, before taking care of the family business, worked in Rome as an architect. The most complex part, solved thanks to the support of an expert, was the administrative procedures for connection to the electricity grid and for obtaining production incentives 'feed in tariff' (ENEL-distributor of electricity, GSE – Energy Service Managing Authority).

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The 2-stage semi-dry plant was entirely supplied by Eisenmann in 2010. The installation was rather simple and quick: it only required some civil works such as the foundations on which it rests, the excavations for the pipes and cable ducts and the network connection works.

The property was personally interested in the choice of technology which fell on a minimally invasive plant. A manufacturer capable of supplying a complete and essentially turnkey plant was chosen. Only for the design of the auxiliary electrical systems it was necessary to contact a specialised designer. There was no problem with the inhabitants of the area.

With regard to plant maintenance, a maintenance contract has been stipulated with a cost of 8-900 €/month which provides for routine and scheduled maintenance every 2,000 hours of operation. The plant produces electricity for over 8,000 hours/year.

In the 13 years of operation, plant shutdowns were almost never necessary apart from scheduled maintenance.

End-use of energy

The electricity produced with biogas is sold into the grid. Part of the hot water is used to heat the digester; in some periods of the year the heat is also used in the process of extracting indigo, a natural dye extracted from the leaves of a legume. The Trionfi Honoati Family is planning to further use the heat for drying the forage and in the milking parlour.

In the first years of life, the plant generated a turnover of around 450,000 €/year with a profit of 30%. More than ten years later, revenues have decreased to just over 300,000 €/year and the margin has dropped to 10% also due to the increase in management costs. However, they represent an important figure for a farm with a turnover of just over €1M.

Overall assessment

The Trionfi Honorati Farm owner, Dr. Antonio Trionfi Honorati, states that the investment risk is quite low: initial revenues and costs are easily predictable; the main variables remain management costs, which have increased considerably in the last decade and, if the company is not self-sufficient, those of supplying substrates.

The income is closely linked to the presence of incentives to produce electricity from renewable sources or biogas. Even if the systems are largely automated, the operation requires a certain commitment and attention.

The plant has allowed the Trionfi Honorati company to take a step forward in terms of sustainability and circularity in resource management. It also gave further visibility to the company, which has become a reference for the area.

The advice of the Trionfi Honorati family to all breeders and farmers is to think about the construction of a biogas plant, that allows for sustainable and virtuous management of zootechnical and agricultural by-products and can also represent an interesting income factor. However, they must be aware that the plant should be sized on the real capacity of the farm and that it also requires additional efforts for its management.

Trionfi Honorati Farm is a very representative case study for what concerns the situation of livestock farms that have biogas plants in Central Italy, where the Marche Region is located. Also in the Marche Region, a predominantly hilly and mountainous area that presents the typical continental climate, the economic conditions, although not as favourable as in the Northern part of Italy, are still quite good for what concerns technological innovation, especially compared to the South and the Islands (Sicily and Sardinia Regions).

Use case 3 - Cupidi Farm (Viterbo, Italy)

Description of the farm and its plant

“Cupidi” is an organic farm owned by Alessio Cupidi and Roberta Leonardi. It is located in Gallese (Viterbo), in the Central Italian Region of Lazio, and was founded in 1997. Since 2006, Cupidi uses Renewable Energies, producing electricity from photovoltaics, and thermal energy from woody biomass (wood chips) using the company’s own pruning.

Figure 29: Dr. Alessio Cupidi showing their photovoltaic panels

Cupidi organic farm, which extends over 2 square kilometres, has a technical production address of zotechnical-energy. The company has 30 years of experience in poultry breeding, and since 2000 has been producing eggs from laying hens. The crops grown on the farm are vines, olive trees and walnut trees. Cupidi is also an educational farm.

Figure 30: Cupidi photovoltaic panels on the stable roof

On the farm there is a photovoltaic system and a biomass pyro gasifier for the production of electricity and a woody biomass plant for thermal energy. The plant has a capacity of 0.020MW/h and produces 63 kW of electric energy per day.

Investment on the plant

The investment for the construction of the plant for RES was 140,000 euros.

The investment was obtained through direct bank financing. The financing problems at the time of the construction of the plant (in 2006) were considerable, as only one bank in Italy knew about the GSE (Energy Service Managing Authority) and its mechanisms.

Authorization process

At the time the plant was built, the authorization process for using renewable energies was extremely long, non-standardized and not clear to interpret, made worse by the fact that there were communication and data transmission problems between crucial Italian energy player ENEL and GSE.

Seven months passed between the end of the plant construction works and the connection to the grid. Cupidi followed the authorization process internally, with the sole support of the documentation provided by the system supplier.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The implementation of the system, which lasted about 10 days, followed an integrative project, using in-house expertise.

The maintenance of the system is performed internally with the help of a trusted electrician.

No difficulties were encountered in relations with neighbouring citizens.

End-use of energy

60% of the electricity produced is used directly, while the rest is sold to the grid. The profit from the sale is around 6000 euros a year.

Overall assessment

The Cupidi case study shows how, according to owner Dr. Alessio Cupidi, the use of renewables is a fairly high-risk investment due to the difficulties encountered in the authorization process, but its managers would definitely do it again, considering that, for a company that practises organic farming, it is also essential to be sustainable from an energy point of view and to arrive as close as possible to autonomy.

Cupidi Farm intends to expand its range of use of renewables, building a new 40 kW plant in a Renewable Energy Community, to feed a company Bugs-farm.

Cupidi's success factors have been the knowledge of the authorization and implementation process for the plant, and the will to manage a production activity that is as sustainable and clean as possible, with products of the highest quality in favour of an attentive and responsible consumer.

The process of transition to the use of renewable energies in Italy could be facilitated by the dissemination of the economic and environmental advantages of this use, as well as certainly by adequate incentives and financing and by fast and clear authorization legislation in this regard.

Cupidi Farm is a very representative case study for the situation of livestock farms that use different Renewable Energy Sources (other than biogas) in Central Italy, where the Lazio Region is located. Also in the Lazio Region, a predominantly hilly area that presents the typical continental climate, the economic conditions, although not as favourable as in the Northern part of Italy or in other Central Regions like Marche or Tuscany, are still quite good for what concerns technological innovation, especially compared to the South and the Islands (Sicily and Sardinia Regions).

Use case 4 - Strovina Bioenergia Farm (Sanluri, Italy)

Description of the farm and its plant

Strovina Bioenergia is a farm located in the South of Sardinia, in Sanluri. It is directed by the agricultural cooperative Strovina 78, that was born in 1978 from the commitment of a group of young farmers who, in years of intense work, managed to bring the uncultivated lands of the ancient "Vittorio Emanuele" factory back into activity.

Figure 31: Strovina 78 Farmhouse

Since 2012, Strovina Bioenergia has been equipped with its own Biogas Cogeneration Plant. At the time of its construction, there were no other biogas plants in Sardinia.

Figure 32: Strovina Bioenergia Biogas Cogeneration Plant

On an area of about 3.5 square kilometres, Strovina Bioenergia Farm mainly deals with sheep breeding, but, in addition to 300 goats, there are also 70 pigs. Cereals are produced: wheat, barley, oats, corn; and so are legumes: broad beans, chickpeas, beans, lentils.

Built in 2012, the Strovina Bioenergia Plant is a single-stage mesophilic plant with a capacity of 1 MWh. All the gas is used in a co-generator. The liquid component of the digestate is stored separately from the solid one. The manure of the animals of Strovina Farm is predominantly used, plus the manure coming from other cattle farms in the area (maximum 5 km). Agricultural and agri-food waste are also used. The overall feedstock composition is 30% manure, 70% agricultural residues and second crops.

By varying the type of composition, there are no great differences in the management and agricultural results of the digestate. It should only be noted that it is possible to obtain a greater quantity of digestate from other agricultural waste placed in co-digestion.

Investment on the plant

The investment for the construction of the plant was €4.5M. No problems were encountered in obtaining the loan: the Maccaferri Group, which built the plant, entered the company by bringing a trusted credit institution, which granted a private loan.

Authorization process

Overall, it took about 2 years to build the plant and the authorization process was the longest part.

The authorization for the electric connection was complicated: there was no capacity, it was built internally by Strovina Bioenergia (they built the power line and then ENEL (owner of the distribution grid) took over it).

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The Maccaferri Group took care of the design of the plant, the choice of the technological supplier and the implementation of the plant.

The decision to implement a biogas plant was made after a careful analysis that took into consideration visits to other plants and Maccaferri's experience. There were no problems with citizens, because neighbors and farmers of the area were involved in advance. The intention to build the plant has never been kept secret, on the contrary an attempt has been made to disseminate information as much as possible also among the inhabitants of the town.

Before starting the authorization procedure, it was necessary to test the ground with local farmers to verify the availability of raw materials.

Regarding the maintenance of the system, for the mechanical part and that relating to the engine, Strovina Bioenergia Farm relies on AB (technology supplier), with whom an ordinary maintenance contract has been stipulated. For the digester, maintenance depends on possible faults and breakages; also in this case it is to AB. Overall, the plant works 8500 hours/year.

End-use of energy

Electricity is produced from biogas and fed entirely into the grid. Some of the heat is used to warm up the digester; another part is distributed through a serpentine under the ground and used to heat about 1000 m² of land used for the production of vegetables, even in winter.

Until 2022, the incentives allowed a good profit. Now, with the increase in prices (services, spare parts, transport, etc.), the business still works but the margins have shrunk a lot.

Overall assessment

The Strovina Bioenergia manager Dr. Andrea Carlotto, member of the cooperative Strovina 78 and of the A2A Group (that acquired the Maccaferri Group), states that the investment for Biogas Plant implementation is not risky and quite profitable.

They sincerely recommend the investment in biogas, and in renewable energy sources in general, to other colleagues in the livestock and farming sector. In fact, it can be considered a profitable low-risk investment since the income of future years and the type of cultivation and breeding that can be exploited are known in advance.

The investment payback has been estimated to be 6-7 years.

The economic prospects of the southern Sardinia area were not very good at the time of the implementation of the biogas plant (2012) and were scarcely predictable. The digester proved to be an element of stability.

At the moment, Strovina Bioenergia does not yet foresee any transformation of biogas into biomethane. However, considering their will to innovate in the field of RES, the managers constantly monitor the Italian legislation in force in this regard to understand if it could be convenient in the future.

Strovina Bioenergia is a very representative case study for the situation of livestock farms that have biogas plants in Insular Italy, where the Sardinia Region is located.

This region, despite being geographically located in the central area of Italy, is assimilated to Sicily (Sardinia and Sicily are the two largest islands in Italy) among the Southern Regions, which are generally more disadvantaged from an economic point of view, and is for this reason that the shift towards the use of RES could represent a big step forward for the territory, albeit more difficult.

Nevertheless, it is important to point out that the Italian government has been trying for some time to promote investments in the Southern regions of the country, providing financial aids for innovation such as the implementation of biogas or biomethane plants.

3.5. Slovakia

Use case 1: Poprad-Matejovce (Poprad – Matejovce, Slovakia)

Description of the plant/farm

The biogas plant Poprad - Matejovce is one of the good examples of efficient use of thermal energy. In addition to the production of electricity from renewable sources, it also supplies hundreds of households with heat. The plant is located in Poprad - Matejovce and belongs to the EnergoTerra, s. r. o., the company which includes two biogas plants (the above-mentioned as well as the biogas plant Huncovce) and seven other farms/agriculture companies engaged in crop and livestock farming in the system of conventional and organic farming. These are operating on 3962 hectares (2023), breed beef cattle (1000 pcs) and sheep without dairy production (2000 pcs).

The biogas plant Poprad - Matejovce was put into operation in 2013 (2011: initial plan, 2012 – 2013: construction). The daily gas output is approximately 12,000 m³/day, which yearly makes it up to the amount of 3,960,000 m³ biogas produced (50% methane).

Figure 33: Poprad-Matejovce plant feedstock

The biogas plant Poprad-Matejovce is an agricultural biogas plant where primarily fermented are plant components such as corn (50% - 15,300 tons/year) and grass silage (20% - 3000 tons/year), and that's in a ratio of 4:1, waste from crop and food production (25% - vegetables and fruits) and manure (5% - cattle manure and chicken manure from Hydinárne Kežmarok). In some cases, also the distillery residues are added.

The biogas plant gets manure from its own farm, but there is also an option to get e.g. chicken manure from a nearby company called Hydinárne Kežmarok (at the price of 6-7€/ton). Firstly, in the

past, chicken manure was given for free, just paying the transport, but now it is paid for. It can be used for the fertilisation, but also as input to the biogas plant.

Figure 34: Manure as a feedstock

The Poprad-Matejovce biogas plant has two generators with the power of 999 kW_{el} installed and 788 kW based upon the above-mentioned feedstock. The purchase of an additional/new heat exchanger is planned in order to increase thermal efficiency. Four people (all men) are taking care of the biogas plant, but about 77 people are employed on the farm (out of which about 15% are female).

All raw materials, weighed already at the time of load (40 tons silage + 10 tons haylage + 5 tons manure), are loaded into the Fliegl container with the capacity of 75m³. The daily load is about 54 ton - 24-times a day, every half an hour. From the container it goes through a feeder, rondo mat and three conveyors (horizontal, inclined and vertical) to the anaerobic digester (multi-stage wet fermentation) with concrete roof. There are three agitators or stirrers in the fermenter/digester.

Figure 35: Poprad-Matejovce plant and technology used

Firstly, the substrate moistening is going on, then three types of bacteria are added. The primary fermentation takes place in the primary digester for approx. 28 days, then in the secondary digester for the next 21 days. The reacted substrate (5500 m³ - separate (outdoors) and fugate (for final storage); digestate - higher proportion of dry matter) are exported by the tankers to the fields as fertiliser - e.g., for stubble after maize.

From the post-fermenter the gas goes to the condensation shaft and clean/dry gas goes into the gas line. The backup generator is needed, because the pumps and agitators or stirrers have to go on continuously so that the substrate doesn't start to sediment after a certain amount of time.

The cogeneration units (CHP) – which co-generate heat as well as electricity - have the standard engine where the combustion part is modified to burn biogas. An integral part of the biogas plant is a transformer station with all the meters measuring everything needed - the amount of electricity, heat going to the grid, amount of heat for their consumption, for technology self-consumption, etc. The other equipment/parts needed are the full burner (3 burners set for different gas richness), engine oil and air conditioner, which cools the gas ideally to 20 degrees (monitoring dew point so that no wet gas goes into the system) with the low-pressure system.

Figure 36: CHP units

Figure 37: Poprad-Matejovce plant

Investment on the plant

The initial investment for the plant implementation was approximately €2.5M with a payback period of 7 years. The plant was built by the previous owner, which was taken over by a new one, who built up an additional biogas plant called Huncovce. This one was the joint investment of the owner and the technology supplier, Agraferm. A 50:50 agreement was reached, where the owner provided input and the technology supplier prepared the feasibility study, calculated the potential based upon the inputs supplied, supplied the know-how, technology and implemented the plant plug and play. The owner has gradually paid the company out.

The funding for the plant implementation was obtained via a financial institution (bank loan) and government subsidies/incentives. The plant implementation was co-financed by the SLOVSEFF programme.

Authorization process

Due to the fact that the plant was built with the plug and play scheme, Agraferm took care of the approval process, with the cooperation of the owner (provided some additions to the required documents), as well. It took over 2 years (from the decision to the first production) to finalize the process, which is considered to be too bureaucratic and inadequate.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The plant was a plug and play installation in cooperation with the company that supplied the technology - Agraferm Technologies AG (all the basic components of the biogas plant were developed and manufactured directly by Agraferm and its partners). Their services cover all steps from planning (preliminary assessments, plant design & optimum layout, project development, profitability calculation, approval process etc.), construction (earthworks, construction of the concrete pits and masonry parts of the building etc.), through the selection and installation of technologies such as piping, installation of stirrers, embedding technology, heating, CHP units etc., to the electrical connection, safety tests and so on.

The owner of the future biogas plant supplied the inputs and Agraferm technology (50:50). Agraferm was gradually paid out by the owner.

During the implementation process and in few cases afterwards as well, they had complaints about traffic, smell (especially when the final storage was being exported), animal noises (not specifically related to the biogas plant), and complaints about land being taken over by purpose-grown energy crops. They have received complaints about surface water pollution, accusations of building an illegal dump (tyres used to cover silage pits), and also received opposition to the building of a facility for the treatment and disposal of biodegradable waste (successful petition). The complaints keep coming despite the fact that village residents participated in the project preparation process in order to refute or clarify their objections.

The plant maintenance is performed by their own people for simple tasks such as when a sensor goes off, but if something more complex or complicated happens (e.g., servicing of CHP units, servicing of biogas plant technology, potential gas leaks, electrical servicing, inspections, etc.), the contracted service companies are call-in. For example, the company that supplies biogas plant Poprad-Matejovce with the engines, provides the maintenance/service as well, so the contract was signed in case of any emergency such as replacement. Inspections, measurements, etc. are set at regular intervals also under the contract.

End-use of energy

The biogas plant Poprad - Matejovce is one of the good examples of efficient use of thermal energy. In addition to the production of electricity (0.99 MW) from renewable sources (which is supplied to the East Slovak Distribution Company, to the grid), it also supplies hundreds of households in Matejovce with the heat. More than 50% of the heat produced is supplied outside the company (in winter this share is close to 80%) - to the adjacent housing estate Poprad-Matejovce (1370 m away), which includes 1000 households and 384 flats, plus a kindergarten and elementary school. This is a

win-win situation for both sides - they need 75% of heat from RES and EnergoTerra s.r.o. has the permanent heat customer.

Biogas plant Huncovce supplies electricity only. The conversion of surplus biogas to biomethane would make sense as it has a good location in terms of connection to the gas grid, but the output would not be sufficient (250-300m³/h). Part of the heat consumption goes for the digester operation, biogas plant technology, heating of admin building and granary/grain dryer.

Overall assessment

If the implementation of a biogas plant can be high or low risk investment depends on a number of factors - such as where the biogas plant is planned or built within or outside the village's internal area; whether there is agricultural production nearby - either crop or livestock production in order to provide sufficient feedstock, etc. It can be profitable provided there is a regular customer; the interviewee stated that they would do it again, but would go directly to a biomethane plant implementation, together with the construction of a whole energy park with alternative sources, like a combination of heat and charging stations, hydrogen, and energy storage.

To Poprad-Matejovce plant' success factors belongs the plant location in relation to the existing infrastructure (existing close to the road - Poprad-Matjovce biogas plant has 2 km from road its central heating system as well as gas pipeline); supply of own raw materials as well as the by-products from other farmers in the area.

Among their recommendations, the implementation of a biomethane plant rather than only biogas, to create the business plan in a way to obtain income from several areas instead of depending on just one, and to reduce artificial fertilisers by 50% giving a bigger possibility to sell digestate.

Use case 2: Borcova biogas plant (Borcová, Slovakia)

Description of the plant/farm

The biogas plant Borcová, built in 2013 and located in Žilina self-governing region in BorcováIt, is the agriculture biogas plant with the 160 hectares of land where rye/hay (800 tons/year), silage corn (at 1,200 tons/year), grasses (2,000 tons/year) are cultivated and cattle, heifers, young cattle (in the average number of 1,000 pieces) are bred. The biogas plant capacity is 1 MW with a gas output of 10,560 m³/day.

Figure 38: Aerial view of Borcova biogas plant

Manure is taken from two large-scale farmers - cattle breeders and this component makes up 40% of the feedstock volume. The manure suppliers come from Borcova surroundings - within a radius of a few kilometres. The chicken droppings are used as well, although they like to avoid it not only because of the excessive smell, but mainly due to the sand found in the droppings, which settles in the agitators/stirrers. The other feedstock is silage maize - mostly from their own production - and haylage from the surrounding fields. However, they can, and often do, process dairy waste, waste from distilling spirits, waste from the baking industry, and biodegradable waste.

In the future, after the transition to biomethane production (the process has already started), the plan is to collect kitchen waste. This will require the completion of a sanitation facility.

The biogas plant is fed with a mixture of the above-mentioned products twice a day. They use two-stage wet fermentation to process these raw materials. The dried gas (without water) then goes to the cogeneration units where the electricity and heat is generated.

Regarding the technology, the Borcova plant uses two-stage wet digester. In addition, they have four 250 kW engines in cogeneration mode that burn biogas and produce heat and electricity. The excess heat is used/ in a dryer and to heat buildings. Two men take care of the facility, 35 employees in the cooperative. The biogas produced is directed to the engines in which it is burned and transformed into electricity (1MW). A small part of it is used for their own purposes and the rest, almost all of it, goes to the grid. A by-product of this production is heat, which they distribute to their community, as

well as is used to heat up a dryer on their premises. Couple of farmers within the premises use the heat to heat up their greenhouses.

Investment on the plant

Borcova plant's initial investment for the implementation was about 4M€. At the time when Borcova's team decided to implement the biogas plant project, agriculture, incl. livestock production, was on the decline. The crop prices were stagnating, and it was very difficult to stay in business, to sustain these activities and operations going. Borcova team therefore decided to use an empty farmyard in the village to build a biogas plant as well as respective infrastructure to give agriculture and livestock production in the area a second wind. The advantage was the electricity connection nearby they can use, plenty of land within a 5 km radius to grow crops that they had access to, and also several cooperatives in the area able to supply them with manure. All these aspects combined led to the decision to go ahead with the biogas plant.

65% of the total investment was covered by a loan and the remaining 35% was their own resources.

Figure 39: Borcova plant digester

Authorization process

The authorisation process took approximately one year with the total fees of 2000€ to 3000€. There were several stages/entities involved such as the municipality, the District Office of the Department of Environment, the Regional Environmental Inspectorate, the Land Fund, the Regional Public Health Office and the Regional Veterinary and Food Administration. The stages of the permits went roughly in order from the zoning procedures, which involved the municipality and the Land Fund, then the environmental impacts, which were assessed by the District Office and the Regional Environmental Inspectorate, and the other permits and hygiene-type inspections from the Regional Public Health Office and the Regional Veterinary and Food Administration. At the end, after construction, there was, of course, the approval procedure. However, the authorization process itself was quite difficult and inadequate. In particular, the preparation of the EIA was complex.

Borcova's team went through the authorisation process itself. The general technology contractor provided the necessary documents, but the team carried out the communication with the authorities

on its own. The biggest challenge was that public administration at that time had only a little to no experience in this field. They were learning things as they went along. Also, certain legislation and certain standards were not set fairly towards facilities of this kind. By modifying legislation and educating officials, many processes could have been streamlined. Mostly, they have overcome those challenges either based on previous experience, or looking for solutions on the spot.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The biogas plant Borcova was built as the integration project – Borcova's team and the general contractor of the upper construction. The earth and concrete works were done by themselves, Borcova team. The general contractor for the upper structure had his own subcontractors who handled the rest of the construction. The technology part was split between two subcontractors. One was in charge of supplying the biogas technology and the other the CHP technology. The biogas plant Borcova team was present during these works and helped whenever needed. Thanks to this, they know now how the system works and can solve many minor problems on their own. So, when it comes to the plant maintenance, the co-generators/CHP technology and major faults are taking care along the supplier line, but otherwise, almost everything is done in-house.

The technology was chosen based upon the financial and space limitations, but also the factor of minimum feedstock consumption (especially corn) needed to be taken into consideration. Also, the maintenance and operational requirements should have been as minimal and as efficient as possible. As they were already planning a district heating system in the village at that time, they went for the technology variant meeting this as well.

After the implementation of the project, they have received some comments from citizens about the traffic load on the road running through the village. However, today they no longer register these comments as the traffic congestion associated with the biogas plant was put to minimum.

End-use of energy

Around 10% is self-consumed and the rest is sent to the grid. The Borcova plant is currently in the process of upgrading to biomethane. To be more specific, in the EIA phase for the connection to the grid of a high-pressure gas pipeline.

The company's profit is only from selling electricity and heat to the community.

Overall assessment

From Borcova plant's point of view, the implementation of a biogas plant is a low or medium risk investment. Borcova's plant big advantage is the ideal location; having the heat consumer and no problem with feedstock, which they can import from a reasonable distance. On the other hand, they can also distribute and use digestate within a reasonable distance. Short transport distances in general are one of the main keys to success. Human capital is also an important factor. They have experienced personnel who can cope with almost any situation. The chosen technology can also handle even difficult raw materials to be processed, which many conventional plants cannot. The feeding and mixing system is good because they can use feedstock with a dry matter content of between 4% and 40%.

Among their recommendations: **(1)** Availability of grid connection with no restrictions or other difficulties is important. The same applies to the connection to the high-pressure gas connection. It

is always necessary to have the land, through which the connections run, sorted out in advance; **(2)** the export of digestate is also the key, a reasonable export distance must be maintained, **(3)** the ratio of input material is also important, they recommend not to exceed the limit of 50% of kitchen waste, and **(4)** in terms of financing, it would be a good idea to look first and foremost to the Eurofunds or Norwegian funds, as the bank financing is still problematic.

Use case 3: Šamorín-Čilistov biogas plant (Šamorín-Čilistov, Slovakia)

Description of the plant/farm

Šamorín-Čilistov biogas plant was built on one and only purpose - to supply the adjacent X-bionic® sphere sports and leisure complex with heat.

The construction of the one-megawatt plant was started by Eco pwr, s.r.o. at the beginning of 2012 and by the end of the same year the plant was completed. After a short test run, the biogas plant was put into permanent operation at the end of December 2012. The company currently has a contract for the connection of the biogas plant to the distribution network in the amount of 0.998 MW of electricity.

Figure 40: Samorin-Cilistov biogas plant

Figure 41: X-bionics sport and relax complex

The biogas plant produces electricity and heat from biogas generated from various feedstocks:

Originally:

- Corn silage (approx. 14 thousand tons).
- Sugarcane bagasse (4 thousand tons).
- Grass haylage.

Cattle slurry - only during the plant start-up phase (approx. 8,000 tones) in order to start the biological process in the digesters.

Currently:

- Maize silage (approx. 16 thousand tons).
- Waste oil and grease traps (from 12/2022).

Biodegradable waste according to Law 79/2015 on waste includes waste animal or plant tissues, animal droppings, urine and manure, cleaning and washing sludge, biodegradable kitchen and restaurant waste, waste from markets, biodegradable waste, edible oils and fats, etc.

Figure 42: Maize silage feedstock 1

The agricultural station has become a biogas municipal station with the following approved inputs:

- Corn silage (10 thousand tons/year).
- Biodegradable waste (10 thousand tons/year).
- Total input raw materials processed (20 thousand tons/year).
- Biomass digestate-fugate output (16,500 m³)

Šamorín-Čilistov biogas plant has several approved input commodities in order not to be limited, but from 2012 until January 2022 they used only one input commodity, namely corn silage. Manure was used only to kick off the process.

For Šamorín-Čilistov biogas plant it makes sense to use manure as feedstock in general, but in their case, the closest cooperative is 30 km away (manure of 5-6% of dry matter and some biogas potential in it, around 30-40 m³ from a ton of manure). This is why using silage has proven to be more effective for them, since they do not have livestock in-house.

Figure 43: Maize silage feedstock 2

Despite the fact that they have also horse manure at their disposal, it's not used as it contains sawdust (used for horses bedding) that the biogas plant cannot process.

The intention is to recover biodegradable waste as well as the biodegradable municipal waste in the total amount of 10,000 tons per year. However, the current maximum plant processing capacity of 20,000 tons per year will not be increased as the recoverable waste will be used as a substitute for the feedstock currently used.

As already mentioned, they do not own a farm, livestock nor land - Šamorín plant does not have its own livestock production. At the beginning, they owned a land of 600 hectares, which was subleased to a local farmer - supplying maize silage to and taking digestate from the plant. Therefore, Šamorín plant is not a typical biogas plant, since all inputs are based on the supply relationships, the outputs, (heat and electricity) are consumed, used or supplied. The electricity produced is supplied to the public grid (ZSE - the West Slovak Distribution Company) on the basis of a Connection Contract. The heat, that is not consumed for its own purposes, is used to supply the adjacent X-bionic® sphere sports and leisure complex.

Figure 44: Aerial view

The biogas station is located in the built-up area next to the local road connecting the Čilistovská road and the recreation area. The biogas plant operates on the principle of wet, two-stage fermentation. It consists of a set of two primary, two secondary digesters and a final storage for digestate/fugate. A gas chamber is located above the final storage.

The cogeneration unit is equipped with a Perkins gas-fired internal combustion engine with an electrical output of 998 kW and 1076 kW_{el}. A Stamford generator is used to generate electricity. Through the transformer station - Schneider transformers - the generated electricity is further processed and transmitted to the ZSE distribution system. All the thermal energy produced, except for the energy needed to keep plant running, is piped to the customer for further use.

Figure 45: Google maps view

The solid biomass enters the plant through a separate dosing point equipped with an 80 m³ feed wagon and mixer. The biogas plant includes a receiving and dispensing point for liquid inputs and digestate dispensing. Digestate, as a high-quality biofertiliser, is exported to the contractual buyer on agrotechnical terms and used for fertilisation.

The gas management of the plant is made up of a gasometer/gasholder supplied by the German company Bauer, a gas pipeline (the biogas path between the digesters, a gasometer, a water separator, a gas cooler, a blower) to the cogeneration unit. The biogas path also includes a burner for emergency gas combustion. The gas path is also secured by liquid pressure relief valves located at all digesters and the final storage.

Figure 46: Siloking feed wagon

The system control/management is fully automated (supplier Energyr). The biogas plant Šamorín - Čilistov has been designed and constructed in a way which allows different compositions of input biomass processed in the four "fermentation paths".

The biogas plant was put into the operation using the latest technologies:

- Source unit/aggregate - PERKINS combustion engine, STAMFORD generator.
- The cogeneration unit of container - was designed for CHP by combustion of biogas from agricultural production in a gas engine. The waste heat generated is mainly used as process heat for the biomass fermentation process. The heat not used in the technological process is piped to the customer for further use.
- Hygienization and sanitation unit 5 m³
- Mixing elements, i.e., EISELE mixers as well as pumps from WANGEN (both German technology).

Nine people work in the biogas plant, in order to ensure the continuous 24-hour operation of the biogas plant technology, including the heat supply to the x-bionic sphere (but not only that). The plant is a source of thermal energy for the sports resort, providing 24-hour service.

Figure 47: Samorin plant's technology

Investment on the plant

The initial plant investment was approx. €4.5M (excluding the current extension of technologies for the treatment of biodegradable waste). Bank financing was used for the plant construction.

Authorization process

As far as the approval process was concerned, they followed standard requirements and legislations. About a year passed between the date of the first application, to the obtention of the building permit approval.

The Šamorín-Čilistov plant's team went through the authorisation process by itself. They built up a team of people set especially for this purpose - e.g., in terms of building permits they worked with design engineers, for approvals in terms of energy they worked with an energy company.

No major challenges, only standard issues arose from building permitting processes.

Figure 48: Samorin plant close-up

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

Šamorín-Čilistov biogas plant was installed on turnkey basis – by an internally tendered (based upon the market research with three price offers) and chosen company (not by public procurement as it was not public funds). The winning company was also the technology supplier. There were no problems with citizens.

In the plant the minor facility maintenance is done by themselves. Major issues are covered by the service contract for servicing the CHP unit.

They faced no problems installing the plant, but a long-term problem with their CHP unit - 3 machine breakages acknowledged by the supplier as a complaint, which means three replacements in 4 years.

The biogas plant was built as part of a sports resort (x-bionic sphere) in order to ensure the independence of the energy source. It was planned as such from the beginning - not to build it as an agricultural plant, but as a source of thermal energy for heating x-bionics' complex. They conducted the feasibility studies themselves, evaluating the price of feedstock, price of thermal energy output in the market and guaranteed price of electricity.

End-use of energy

The treated biogas is fed to a cogeneration unit. Almost 90% of the electricity is supplied to the public grid. The energy in the form of heat is used to heat the premises of the plant, to ensure temperature maintenance in the digesters (10%) and to heat the adjacent Olympic Training Centre (90%).

In addition to biogas and energy outputs, the biogas plant also generates a material output (digestate), which is generally permitted as a secondary source of nutrients and used for fertilization in agricultural operations. This is delivered to the maize silage supplier, a win-win situation for both parties.

Figure 49: X-bionics complex

Regarding the upgrading of biogas to biomethane, the plant's team is in the process of assessing which direction to take. The engine is due for a major overhaul, so they are working on potential models for a change of source, that can be either a new combustion engine or the implementation of biogas to biomethane upgrading.

As biogas plant, Šamorín is a bit specific, since they earn minimal profit in its operation, which will probably have to be re-invested for the renewal of the technology.

Overall assessment

Looking at the Šamorín-Čilistov case, they are not sure if they would recommend the implementation of a biogas plant, unless the investor is also an agricultural producer and owns livestock as well.

Moreover, investment in a biogas plant under the conditions offered by the legislator today would, from their point of view, no longer make sense. What makes sense today, and why they are also working on the transformation, is the environmental value: the transformation from a purely technical raw material such as maize or manure to a commodity raw material.

However, for waste and its disposal, operators will need to build up/complete other costly facilities. Šamorín plant already processes oil and fat, but only in a very minority share. It does not even replace 1% of the total input. For example, there is an acute shortage of waste input, the supply of usable waste is questionable, and the waste market is not functioning yet properly. They have the advantage of being close to the capital (Bratislava).

The transformation of the biogas plants into a waste treatment facility will take some time. A technological upgrade is needed, even though we already have a sanitation unit. They are currently considering which technologies they will have to refinance and which technologies to abandon. A

call for support in this area is expected to be announced - June or July 2023, although no one knows when exactly that will be and under what conditions. They are planning to participate in this call.

Figure 50: Samorin-Cilistov biogas plant

When asked about their success factors, they specified they could not provide any at the moment because success is calculated in “the end” and they felt they still had a long way to go, and are willing to continue in this road. Currently, they are contributing to the green ambition: to recover 100% of our residual heat, not just on paper or just to meet legislation, using their biogas plant to generate heat for an existing customer site.

Most importantly, the implementation of the plant has confirmed that if there are any fluctuations in the energy market again, they can bridge this period and produce heat at a stable price. Of course, they depend directly on raw material inputs, but if they diversified these, it is not expected that fluctuations in the exchange price of electricity or gas would have an immediate impact on their

activities. With 15,000 tons of waste and 5,000 tons of maize per year, we would be able to stabilize the demands that the resort has, so they strongly recommend diversifying the sources of feedstock.

3.6. Spain

Use case 1: Mouriscade Estate (Lalín, Spain)

Description of the plant/farm

The estate is located in Lalín, in Pontevedra a province of Galicia, Spain (north of the country). It consists of **(1)** a laboratory with specialized professionals in livestock nutrition and prevention of diseases, **(2)** a farm where they work on the genetic improvement of embryo, so the best specimens of calves are born there thanks to the researchers work, **(3)** a biogas plant where the waste generated by the cattle is used to produce energy, and **(4)** lands for agriculture, especially destined for corn plantations. In total, the estate has 40 Ha available for farming, but the biogas plant is located in a sub parcel of the farm.

The plant was implemented in 2013, and it produces biogas using cattle manure and other agricultural waste (such as fodder) as feedstock, obtained from farming exploitation in the farm via anaerobic digestion. In this case, the capacity of the design corresponds with the size of the cattle farm, which accounts for 100 heads of cattle, which is the typical size of a farm in the Galicia region.

The feedstock used comes exclusively from the Mouriscade farm. The manure is transported via gravity, while other types of feedstocks are brought by tractor. Around 1,600 ton of manure and fodder are treated in the plant a year.

The digester (257 m³) has been built in concrete and incorporates a flexible cover that allows the accumulation of biogas. Through a stirring system, the nutrients are distributed homogeneously before being introduced in the digester in a pre-treatment tank of 12 m³. The co-generation equipment is an internal combustion engine (CHP).

All the resulting digestate is used as in-house fertilizer, and the average electric generation is around 150 MWh_{el} a year, which is all consumed in-house.

Figure 51: Digester in the construction stage [3]

Figure 52: Biogas plant in the Mouriscade Estate

Investment on the plant

The plant was implemented with the association of the Mouriscade Farm (livestock farm and laboratories owned by the Pontevedra council) with the Xunta de Galicia (automic government of the region) and Energylab (technological centre). The plant was financed via a public investment of €245,000, with a payback time of 7 years.

Authorization process

Although the authorization process in Spain varies per autonomous community, since one of the stakeholders of the plant is a governmental body, not many challenges were faced regarding the authorization phase.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

The implementation of the plant was carried out by the Xunta de Galicia, and they outsourced the necessary procedures to interested organizations, when necessary, like design of the plant, permit applications, among others.

End-use of energy

The energy produced is used in the form of electricity as a supply for the farm, covering almost 60% of their electric consumption.

Overall assessment

The Mouriscade Estate is one of the best-known cases of a biogas plant from manure in Spain, and it has been functioning since 2013. The plant is capable of generating savings of around 190,000 kWh a year, and also stops around 60 tonnes of CO² from going into the atmosphere. It seems to be a successful collaboration model between livestock farmers, technology centres and governmental bodies, and a promising way of reducing the impact of challenges like the bureaucratic processes and securing finance.

Among their success factors, they valorise thermal energy as well as electric energy for their in-house use, and of course do not miss the opportunity of using the digestate as fertilizers for their own crops.

Use case 2: Torre Santamaría Farm (Vallfogona de Balaguer, Spain)

Description of the farm

The Torre Santamaría farm is a family farm located in Vallfogona de Balaguer (Lleida) in Catalonia, Spain. They produce around 24M litres of milk a year, and it is one of the first cattle-milk farms to be auto-sufficient regarding electricity by turning their waste into biogas, and the **very first Spanish farm to produce biomethane in-house**.

By using their biogas plant within their own farm, the manure of around 2,300 cattle is used to obtain biomethane via anaerobic digestion. A mechanical system gathers the manure, which travels underground until a pre-treatment tank where the organic waste is stirred until ready to introduce in the digester in liquid form (each digester has a 10,000 m³ capacity, they have a total of 4).

The result is a gas (biogas) made of 54% methane, and the rest is CO₂ and others, which is later purified in an upgrading plant to obtain the biomethane, which can be injected in the grid directly. Thanks to this system, the farm has reduced their GHG emissions to nearly zero, and they are obtaining extra income with the generation of biomethane.

Figure 53: Torre Santamaría farm

Figure 54: Biogas and biomethane plants in Torre Santamaría

Investment on the plant

The investment to implement the plant was private, around €4M, and was financed in collaboration with the company Axpo Iberia, via the first ever purchase contract of biomethane model (for the long-term) in Spain. Axpo was one of the first operators in commercializing biomethane in Spain in 2015, and they support these types of agreements in order to boost the investment in biogas and biomethane technologies.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

In 2011 the farm was one of the first to install digestors to produce biogas from cattle manure, being able to meet the energy needs of the farm to a 100% regarding electricity, heating, and hot water.

In 2020, Torre Santamaría reached an agreement with Axpo Iberia, in which the purchase contract for biomethane for the long-run was signed between them, a first of its kind for the country. With this first €4M investment, Torre Santamaría was able to modernize the plant installations and adapt the plant for the upgrade of biogas to biomethane.

As of 2023, Axpo Iberia and Sorigué (ESCOs) have acquired 80% of the plant (each have 40%, with Torre Santamaría having the remaining 20%), and are planning on investing extra €15M in the project. This is expected to increase production to 115 GWh a year.

End-use of energy

The end-use of the energy produced is for in-house consumption, and together with other 3 Axpo Iberia plants they account for around 30GWh of the gas injected to the grid annually in Lleida. As of 2023, it is expected that they will increase the 73,000 tons a year processing capacity to 200,000 tons a year, so they expect to keep growing in capacity.

Overall assessment

The Torre Santamaría farm is the first farm to produce biomethane from livestock manure in Spain, and one of the few case studies identified in the country that injects energy into the grid. Together with Axpo Iberia, they have created a model to finance the investment of the plant that also allows the local energy companies to take advantage of the remaining renewable gas produced in the farm, boosting the investment in renewable energy that Europe desperately needs.

These types of collaborations and investments have been essential for the upgrade of the initial biogas plant they first implemented, and have allowed them to continue growing the business, benefiting several stakeholders in the process, and contributing at the same time to renewable energy generation.

Promoting the use of livestock and agricultural waste to generate biogas and biomethane is the key to decrease the disposal of the waste in the fields, which is a recurring problem in the country. For these technologies to be able to expand to the rest of the country, it becomes necessary to create a certification of origin system, which gives more value and differentiates gas obtained from renewable sources from fossil alternatives.

Use case 3: Purines Almazán Plant (Almazán, Spain)

Description of the plant/farm

Located in Almazán in the province of Soria in Castile and León due to the high concentration of porcine and poultry farms dedicated to the breeding and fattening of the animals. In this area, the livestock waste generated in all farms was traditionally used as fertilizer.

Figure 55: Purines Almazán waste treatment plant

However, in the last years this system has evolved, going towards making these animals bigger in the less time possible, which requires a specific food requirement and a high-water consumption, which inevitably also impacts the volume of waste generated. Spain in general is facing a challenge regarding the disposal of livestock waste in the country, since they constitute a big environmental issue due to the high volume of manure generated and their contaminant contents.

In order to tackle this problem, the Regional Government of Castile and León (maximum governmental body of the region) decided to implement a bioenergy centre, including a plant for the treatment of manure, completely focus in using agricultural and livestock waste and repurposing it for its use in the sector and also for energy generation.

The manure used as feedstock in the plant comes around 40,000 and 25,000 headcounts of pigs and poultry, respectively. The process includes:

1. The use of a pre-treatment: the reception tank has a 500 m³ capacity and works with submerged bombs that send the manure through the different stages which separate the solids from the liquids.
2. An anaerobic treatment: the fundamental phase where the two concrete digestors of 1,200 m³ come in place. The fundamental characteristic of the process is that it lacks mechanical stirring. The mixing is done via the sequential opening and closure of an automatic valve connected to the gas collector.
3. Aerobic treatment: this acts as a refining treatment, and it is designed using a lagoon system.
4. Energy generation: a motor generator of 240 kW is fed by the biogas generated from the digestion process, since this gas is ready to be used for energy generation, to be stored or to burn. The energy production is estimated to be 3,300 kWh a day.

It was first built in 2009, had to shut down in 2014 and was re-activated in 2019 (further explained in section below: implementation and maintenance of the plant).

Figure 56: Purines Almazán Plant (another view)

Investment on the plant

The waste treatment plant is a collaboration work of the Service for Environmental Protection of the Regional Government of Castile and León, Provincial Government of Soria, Almazán City Hall, and consultancies like ADAUX (phase 1) and CADAGUA (phase 2 and 3).

The land was donated by the Almazán Council, and around €6M of public funding was invested to build this plant back in 2009, provided by the Regional Government of Castile and Leon and the Provincial Government of Soria.

Authorization process

The authorization process was carried out by the Almazán City Hall (participant in the implementation), who is the responsible body for this process in the region, so it was not a challenge. After the shutdown, Naturgy (the reactivating party) applied for an extension of all the permits necessary, due to the long-time inactive, it had to go through an extra municipal control.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

As mentioned previously, the plant was implemented by the government of Castile and León, and its location was strategical in order to receive the transported manure from the nearby farms. The feedstock is transported in tanks, supporting farms located in Matamala de Almazán, Viana de Duero, Baniel and Almazán.

On 2014, after the withdrawal from the government's aid for the production of electricity from pig manure, the plant was shut down for the next 5 years. This situation affected this and many other plants in the country, hindering the growth of the sector, including all other plants in the region (Soria). In 2019, Naturgy (energy company) has activated the plant again, and it's working now 24/7 with 8 workers on-site.

End-use of energy

The plant has the capacity to treat 90,000 tons of manure annually. They sell 26% of the energy generated, and the rest is used in-house as electric and thermal energy. With this scheme, they cover 75% of the plant's electricity needs.

Overall assessment

A case for many of the plants implemented in Spain before 2014, the removal of the government aid for electricity generation from manure left many biogas plants using manure as feedstock in a difficult position, with many having to stop operations completely due to these constraints. Situations like this have contributed with the slow development of the sector in the country, but since then, the number of biogas and biomethane plans has slowly started to raise, but the many regulatory authorization constraints still present a challenge for livestock farmers and other stakeholders.

Thanks to the interest of energy companies in investing in renewable energy, some plants like Almazán Plant have received extra investment in order to start functioning again. This validates the previous challenge pin-pointed for Spain as a country regarding the challenge that the lack of incentives for stakeholders and farmers to invest in biogas represents, nevertheless, there is a lot of biogas potential in Spain and the sector continues to grow, even if slowly.

For the case of this plant, as like for many other cases identified in the country, the participation of a governmental body in the "association of stakeholders" seems to be key for the authorization process to present less of a challenge.

3.7. Czech Republic

Bonus Use case: Bioinvest Kunčina, AGRO Kunčina, Bioinvest Pacov (Kunčina, Czech Republic)

Description of the plant/farm

It is a family business that combines the agriculture (AGRO Kunčina, BIOINVEST Kunčina Ltd, BIOINVEST Pacov - the agricultural cooperatives) with the renewable energy sector (three biogas plants and solar power plant installed). The latest mentioned was installed by SUNFIN PRAHA s.r.o. company which is owned by the same family. SUNFIN PRAHA installed its first photovoltaic project with an installed capacity of 0.25 MWp on the roofs of the AGRO Kunčina cooperative as early as 2008, which was subsequently expanded to include other solar power plants in the Kunčina cadastre. A year later, in 2009, the first biogas plant was built on the cooperative premises, followed by two more three years later (in 2012) with cooperation by AgriKomp Bohemia company (plug & play) and the total capacity of 2,5 MW:

- Biogas plant Kunčina: 0,75 MW(with an expansion to 1 MW is in progress).
- Biogas plant AGRO Kunčina: 1 MW.
- Biogas plant Pacov: 0,5 MW.

After completion and construction in the cadastre of the Kuncčina village, these are among the unique buildings of this kind in one area - combining two RES sources (bioenergy - biomass and solar energy).

Figure 57: BIOINVEST Kuncčina with solar power plant

As it is a family business, the feedstock for the biogas plants is supplied by the cooperatives and the adjacent farms: AGRO Kuncčina operates on 3,000 hectares of land, which supplies feedstock such as corn/maize silage (80%), grass haylage (15%) and slurry/manure (5%) for both biogas plants in Kuncčina. The AGRO Kuncčina cooperative breeds about 500 pcs of cattle.

Pacov plant's raw material used is 50% silaged GPS, 20% grass haylage and 30% maize silage - produced by Arnoštov s.r.o. farm and Městečko Trnávka. In Pacov cca 300 pcs of sheep are bred and their manure represents the feedstock for Pacov's plant.

From the feedstock's point of view, they are completely self-sufficient.

In both of Kuncčina's biogas plants there are two primary digesters (two in each), plus a secondary digester. The digesters are equipped with a Biolene® biogas storage membrane. Biolene® is a gas storage tank and fermenter/digester cover in one and thus offers a highly efficient solution for small agricultural and industrial biogas plants. The Biolene® system is made of high-quality EPDM rubber. This material is characterised by its high resistance to UV, ozone and high temperatures, as well as its high flexibility and durability.

Figure 58: BIOINVEST Pacov

Among other technologies used belong the heat exchangers, CHP units, two containers of the Vielfras brand in both Kuncina's plants - seamless dosing of raw materials into the fermenter/digester is a technological challenge. For example, feedstocks for renewable energy production often contain stones and sand, which can increase wear and failure rates. Dosing solid manure and long-fibre grass silage can therefore place a limiting burden on the technology. The Vielfraß® solids dosing system from agri-Komp is specially designed to meet these demands - it is based on two counter-rotating augers with knives, which ensure loosening and mixing of the substrate. Also, the Quetsch Profi® separator is used with infinitely variable dry solids adjustment. The separator can be used not only to separate digestate from biogas production, but also to separate slurry, where the solid fraction can be used back for bedding.

Investment on the plant

The plant's investment was about €3.2M approximately. Initially, there was only the original biogas plant on the cooperative built in 2009 thanks to massive support at that time, in the form of an investment subsidy. In cooperation with agriKomp, a turnkey biogas station construction company, the idea to build another plant with an output of 0.75 MWh was born. The entire process - from the feasibility study, project documentation, authorization process, incl. the processing of building permits to the actual plant construction, as well as technology design and delivery where the individual components are coordinated in detail with each other - was taken care by the AgriKomp Bohemia company.

The plants were funded via a bank loan, the green bonus scheme and in the case of AGRO Kunčina plants also the investment incentives - government subsidies (2009) were playing a role.

There was no problem with financing.

Authorization process

Obtaining EIA (Environmental Impact Assessment) process went relatively quickly. The study of environmental impact assessment was handled by the Regional Office of Environment in Pardubice.

Based upon EIA, other permits were obtained. Everything was taken care of by the AgriKomp company and the whole process took about one year, no major challenges faced there.

Implementation and maintenance of the plant

As previously mentioned, it was plug & play plant, and the whole process was implemented by AgriKomp Bohemia company, including the design and delivery of the technology.

During the plant installation, there were no issues with citizens in Kuncina, although in Pacov there was a civic hearing/public meeting in order to clarify the terms. Information on the public bulletin board included the word GPS - people were afraid that the plant will process GPS devices). So, the meaning of GPS needed to be explained - not Global Positioning System but harvesting & using the green plants (the whole plant, except the roots) for fodder, forage for renewable energy production (e.g., production of bio-mass from green maize). There were also complaints about smell, which were resolved through installation of air fresheners with forest smell. Plus, frequency measurement of noise was introduced.

The simple maintenance tasks are taken care by the biogas plant service staff (4-5 people in all three plants), possibly SUNFIN's electricians. But more complex issues are in the provision of agriKomp Bohemia and its service company - online/offline service according to fault and need. The regular maintenance and servicing within the time limits laid down by law are done by agriKomp as well. The measurements of oil, or e.g., sugar potential, etc. are in the hands of certified laboratories. No problems regarding installing/maintaining the equipment encountered.

End-use of energy

On-site electricity use is in the amount of 1-5% (depending on which plant we are talking about - the AGRO Kunčina plant supplies electricity to a sawmill, the other Kunčina plant supplies about 5 households in the vicinity), but 95-99% goes to the grid/electricity distribution network.

The heat is used for the heating of (a) the area where the sheep are kept (biogas plant Pacov), (b) wood drying premises, (c) heating of administrative buildings; d) supplying heat to the above-mentioned households, and (e) the tennis hall heating (close to Kunčina plant).

Figure 59: BIOINVEST Kuncina

Overall assessment

BIOINVEST Kuncina assures that it's not about profitability, rather a sort of a "love affair" with RES or agricultural energy per se. Compared to solar or PV panels, a biogas plant is a much more technical and service intensive option.

When it comes to success factors, they consider that mutual trust is a definitive factor, either in the family, or in the company as it is a family business, the same applying for business partners. And finally, the other success factor is their love for renewable energy sources.

They recommend using alternative sources or a combination of them - e.g., biogas, PV, solar power plants, energy storage, battery or other.

4. Insights

The case studies chosen covered different geographies in order to offer a broad approach to the analysis, the intention was to include farms and plants from different regions in each country to be able to obtain an integral feel of the context for each ALFA region.

Overall, the case studies were able to validate limiting factors already identified by the consortium, such as covering investment costs, difficulty with the authorization processes, and quality of feedstock all playing a role in the success and feasibility of implementing biogas plants in the country. Additionally, regional differences in regulations and resource availability of course also impact the adoption of biogas technology.

However, new many recommendations were provided by the interviewees. Among the recommendations to other interested farmers/stakeholders:

Insights/Recommendations from Belgium

- Take into consideration the daily work and maintenance required to run a biogas plant (maintenance of engines can require extensive attention).
- The repayment period for the type of plants studied is around 6-7 years, although the cost varies on the technology chosen.
- Conduct around 4-5 analyses of the manure before installation of the plant in order to assess the true biogas potential.
- Overall, the quality of fresh manure is essential, and liquid manure is easier to work with than thick manure.
- Prioritizing the use of animal waste and minimizing extra processing.
- When speaking about biomethane, it is essential to assess the amount of energy that can be injected to the grid to know how much biogas to upgrade.
- The simplification of regional regulations and requirements and the addressing of manure transporting issues is key to facilitate replication.

Insights/Recommendations from Denmark

- In the country it is a good business to run a biogas plant, and all the successful cases interviewed would do it again without a doubt.
- It is necessary to have both technical and authorization-process support when establishing a plant, and also to secure the biomass base.

Insights/Recommendations from Greece

- The success of the cases was thanks to their relation and collaboration with analytical laboratories and other key partners that bring value to the investment.
- Many are able to stay relevant with their participation in many research projects, accessing innovative technologies.

- Take time to do the proper initial design, operation and maintenance plans for the plant, as well as mind for the quality of the raw materials, since minding these conditions can lower the risk of investment.
- One success factor identified is the high solid concentration in the production process, which is not common for all plants.

Insights/Recommendations from Italy

- An identified success factor is the perfect integration of the biogas plant with a farm, making it a circular economy system.
- Challenges identified are data transmission problems with energy managers, and also bureaucratic administrative issues.
- One advice for farmers is to really consider the construction of biogas plants as the sustainable management of animal and agricultural by-products and waste which can turn into an income factor.
- It is recommended that the plant is sized according to the real farm capacity and needs.
- A big plus is the previous knowledge of authorization and implementation process.

Insights/Recommendations from Slovakia

- It is best to also implement a biomethane plant from the beginning instead of only biogas plant.
- It is recommended to obtain income from different sources and not only one.
- The availability of grid connection with no restrictions nor difficulties is important.
- Regarding financing, look for Eurofunds or Norwegian funds, since bank financing is still problematic.
- Diversify feedstock as much as you can, and also diversifying sources of renewable energy.

Insights/Recommendations from Spain

- Implementation seems to be more successful when there is a public entity related to the financing/implementation of the project, since this eases the bureaucratic processes and lowers the number of challenges in this regard.
- The valorisation of thermal and electric energy is a success factor identified for the country, since the practice of obtaining energy from manure is not common yet, in this way it is a best practice to be able to cover all the in-house energy consumption with RES. Also, the valorisation of the digestate as high-quality fertilizer.
- The model of cooperation with energy companies has been taking off in the country, with more and more interest from ESCOs to invest in biogas, making them a reliable partner when looking for financing opportunities.
- Only two of the case studies inject energy to the grid (the other only cover their own consumption), which is a reflection that the development of biogas coming from manure in the country is immature yet but is getting there slowly.

5. Conclusions

The study was carried to validate the challenges that each region is facing, which were already identified via previous tasks, and for, more importantly, get to know how the cases of successful implementation of the obtention of biogas from manure have faced and solved these problems.

Some differences have been found between regions, evidencing that the six countries' adoption rates for biogas technology differ significantly from one another. However, the study was able to identify some interesting recommendations and facts about each region's uptake methods for biogas technologies and overall feel with the uptake of biogas coming from manure.

The study identified several benefits associated with biogas adoption, such as the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, improved energy security, and the production of organic fertilizers. In general, issues like the high capital cost of biogas plants (and difficulties for financing) and the bureaucracy from the authorization and implementation processes remains as the main barriers for adoption, particularly for small-scale farmers. This highlights the biogas potential of each region, but also brings a necessity for a call to action for coordinated efforts by policymakers, industry stakeholders, and financial institutions to overcome the barriers to adoption and support the scaling up of biogas technology.

6. References

- [1] B. C. S. M. S. C. M. S. D. S. D. A. Facci E.G. et al, «Framework and value chain conditions affecting the biogas in livestock farming (Under review),» 2023.
- [2] E. I. Bank, JESSICA, 2007.
- [3] L. N. Balseiro, «Planta de biogás: Finca Mouriscade [Biogas plant: Mouriscade Estate],» 2012.

7. Annex

A1. Eligibility criteria

ALFA – Case studies eligibility criteria

The base eligibility criteria presented below is the minimum necessary a success case needs to comply with according to the DoA. These base conditions are the ones we must ensure to comply with project KPIs and objectives.

Base eligibility criteria

All 3 must be met:

- ✓ **Based at least in one of the ALFA hub countries:** Greece, Denmark, Slovakia, Italy, Belgium, or Spain. *If we catch interest of an interesting case belonging to another country, we can include it as an extra case, but we must focus on finding the 3 success cases per region first.*
- ✓ **That they agree to participate through consent form and/or written form:** Similarly, as it was done for the interviews, a consent form will be drafted to use their information for the project's purpose. *If the plant/farmer/cooperative wants to remain anonymous for any reason, the consortium will come up with a solution to approach the situation, but the initial proposition is that they agree to be promoted as a success case publicly. However, until we know how many cases we have in total, let's not disregard them if they wish to remain anonymous.*
- ✓ **Be one of the following stakeholders:**
Livestock farmers/Farmer groups/Cooperatives that produce biogas **OR Biogas plants successfully cooperating with livestock farmers in other ways** (service contracts or other business models, this could vary regionally) **OR Livestock farmers/Farmer groups/Cooperatives that use other RES*** for livestock farming. Any biogas plant considered **must use manure as one of their feedstocks** (they can use other sources as long as they also use manure).

**Would be useful to engage at least one success story per region of a farmer/cooperative that uses other renewable energy sources for comparison.*

Prioritization criteria (to determine “more favorable” over “less favorable”)

The suggestion is to start identifying potential success stories that comply with the **base eligibility criteria**. However, if a partner has identified many options and wishes to further filter them, the following list shows the order of relevance to use as a guide:

1. **Gender balance** (there are many male participants in the interviews from previous tasks, so if one case involves more women participation than other, it should be favored).
2. **Upgrade to biomethane:** If the stakeholder upgrades biogas to biomethane, it should be favored since the number of biomethane plants when comparing to biogas plants is lower, it could give a different perspective to the studies.
3. **Use of cutting-edge technology:** If they are using state-of-the-art processes, machinery, or techniques (in relation to the innovation level of the region being considered, of course).
4. **Geographical:** Select cases that are distributed in different regions of the country (e.g. favor 1 case in city A and one case in city B, versus 2 cases in city A).
5. **Cases with different approaches:** have different types of use for biogas.
6. **Cases that use different sources of feedstock** (e.g., one for pig manure, other for cattle manure, etc).
7. **Cases with different approaches:** livestock farms that use other RES.

If the need to choose arises, each partner will go through the list above with their potential cases. If they both comply with gender balance, then move down to the next condition. If they both also upgrade biogas to biomethane, then move to the next condition and so on, until one complies with more characteristics than the other.

If they both comply with the same number of characteristics and the partner must make a choice between them, then they can choose the one they are closest to or believe would be easier to schedule the interview and any other following interactions. If a partner wants to pursue more than 3 cases (e.g: a partner finds 4 great cases and they fulfill all conditions), there is no problem in analyzing more studies.

The final number of cases needed by region is at least 3. The cases to be initially identified will be **6 per ALFA region**, to guarantee some room in case not all cases are interested.

Once the case studies have been identified, the partner in charge of the corresponding hub will contact the first 3 options of their list. If the potential cases do not reply or do not agree, then we move to the following 3. If they deny participation, then we will look for successful cases that comply with the base criteria only, until we find the 3 cases.

A2. Case study guide questionnaire

Questionnaire/interview guide for successful cases

Interviewee information

Name of interviewee:

Age of interviewee:

Gender of interviewee:

Role in the farm/cooperative/association:

Photo of the interviewee: *Optional (for promotion purposes)*

Logo of the cooperative/association: *In case there is a logo, optional.*

1. Describe your plant

Plant name: *Name of plant.*

Location: *Country, city (or region).*

Year of plant construction: *Year.*

Size of farm and type of livestock: *Approx number (in a measuring unit, m², Ha, Km²) and type of animals.*

Plant capacity: *MWh*

Gas output (if applicable): *m³/day*

Photo of the plant: *Up to the interviewee: a photo that showcases the technology, the location and/or the animals would be nice, but of course open to whatever picture they send us.*

Processes and workflow: *How do they operate? Where do they get the manure? Do they have agreements with farmers nearby? Is a farmer part of the stakeholders of the plant? How are those agreements?*

Technologies used: *What technology do you use? What type of digester? Does your plant/farm operate with any state-of-the-art technology? If yes, which one? What is the innovation and added value of said technology?*

End-use for biogas produced (if applicable): *e.g. burned on-site to heat buildings, used on the digester or used on site as electricity and/or gas, sold to the electricity/gas grid, generation of compressed natural gas or liquified natural gas, or any other applications.*

How many people work in the plant (if possible, please, divide by gender): *Approx. number.*

2. Investment

Upfront investment for the plant implementation: *Approx. number*

What did you do to direct the decision to implement the plant? *What was the thought process or analysis behind implementation? Market analysis? Did you hire someone to undertake feasibility study, profitability of investment, etc? how did you find him/her?*

How did you obtain the funds for the implementation? Did you have problems finding funding? *Government incentives, financing entity, bank, technology provider acting as stakeholder, etc*

3. Authorization process

Can you describe the authorization process? *Stages, organisms, fees, how long was this process?*

Did you carry out this process yourself or via a consultant/engineer/other party?

What were the main challenges of this process? *Lack of standardization, complexity of the process itself and/or legislation/regulation, etc*

How did you overcome those challenges? *Hiring a consultant/company for the application, finding someone experienced in this process to carry out the application, etc*

4. Implementation and maintenance of the plant:

How did you implement the plant? *Under what scheme? Plug and play plant, integration project, etc, and how long was it to implement?*

How did you choose the technologies implemented? *Consultant/engineer hired, in-house expertise, etc*

Did you have any issues with citizens in the plant implementation? *Opposition to the implementation, complaints after implementation on odor/noise, etc*

How do you perform the plant maintenance? *Maintenance of the technology, livestock, etc*

Any problems in installing/ maintaining the plant? *Finding someone to undertake the technical study? Finding the right technology providers? Local professionals have the knowledge for maintenance?*

5. End-use of renewable energy

Do you sell the energy/gas to the grid or use it for self-consumption? In what percentage? *(e.g. sell half and use half in-house)*

Do you upgrade biogas to biomethane? Or plan to upgrade? *Yes/No*

How much do you make from using biogas or another type renewable energy? *Approx. number or percentage of total. E.g. if they make X euros a year with their business/farm/cooperative, what percentage of X comes from selling electricity/gas to the grid, etc*

6. Advice for replication

Is implementing a biogas/renewable energy plant a high or low risk investment? Is it profitable? Would you do it again? *Ask them to briefly explain why if possible.*

What are your success factors? *What makes you different, what do you think has made the difference in the process of implementing these technologies?*

What would your recommendations be to fellow professionals seeking to implement biogas/renewable energy technologies? *e.g. how would they do it if they wanted to implement other plants? What could ease the process? Incentives, legislation and regulatory frameworks, accessibility to funding sources, etc*

A3. Example of template for promotion of case studies

Successful cases of producing renewable energy in livestock farming

LIVESTOCK FARMS

[Name of farm – e.g. El Pozo farm (Andalusia, Spain)]

WHAT ANIMALS LIVE IN THEIR FARM?

WHO ARE THEY?

Brief introduction to the farm, location, a brief opening, when was it founded, etc (this info may vary from case to case) ([section 1 of questionnaire](#))

LAND AND CLIMATE

Basic info, type of land and climate in the region.

HOW DO THEY FARM?

How does the farm interoperate? What animals/products do they focus on? How many people work there? What do they do with the manure? Any agreements in place with biogas plants or other models? Do they cultivate anything? ([section 1 of questionnaire](#))

[Name of farm – e.g. El Pozo farm (Andalusia, Spain)]

How do you produce biogas? How was the investment funded?

THEIR APPROACH TO RENEWABLE ENERGY SOURCES

What RES are they incorporating to livestock farming? Biogas? Another type? Explain the technology they use, and how they operate this technology, what feedstock is used, where they obtain it, etc (section 1 of the questionnaire)

AVERAGE UP-FRONT INVESTMENT

XX €

HOW WAS THE INVESTMENT FUNDED?

How was the investment funded? Short explanation of problems they faced finding the money and how they overcame them (section 2 of the questionnaire)

Funded by the European Union

[Name of farm – e.g. El Pozo farm (Andalusia, Spain)]

How long did it take (from idea to implementation)?

AUTHORIZATION PROCESS

Brief description of the process and government bodies involved, the challenges faced and how they overcame them (section 3 of questionnaire)

IMPLEMENTATION

Scheme of implementation, who did it, how did they choose the technologies to be implemented? Problems faced (e.g. finding tech providers, local professionals, adapting to local feedstock, etc.) and how they overcame them (section 4 of questionnaire)

END-USE OF RENEWABLE ENERGY

What do they do with the Energy generated? Connection to the grid? Used in-house? Upgrade to biomethane? How much do they make from using RES as a percentage of total? (section 5 of questionnaire)

Funded by the European Union

ALFA

[Name of farm – e.g. El Pozo farm (Andalusia, Spain)]

What would you recommend to others trying to produce biogas from manure?

THEIR 101 FOR SUCCESSFUL IMPLEMENTATION

Here we include the main findings of each case regarding the advice they have for others, would they do it again? How would they do it? What are the success factors they have identified? Other recommendations, etc (section 6 of questionnaire)

The project

ALFA has the objective to help unlock the EU's biogas production potential by fostering the adoption of technologies using manure to produce biogas, thus helping increase the adoption of renewable energy sources in the EU and helping reduce emissions from untreated animal waste. The project will identify drivers and barriers for the uptake of biogas in the EU livestock farming industry and will support farmers from 6 EU countries (Italy, Denmark, Belgium, Slovakia, Greece and Spain) through its own co-created solutions, including financial, business, and technical support services as well as capacity-building seminars. In parallel, the project will develop an Engagement Platform to host tools that facilitate collaboration and knowledge exchange among industry actors and provide credible estimations of each farm's biogas potential, prospect profits, and environmental and social impacts. Moreover, ALFA will inform all relevant stakeholders via awareness-raising campaigns and policy recommendations, and will provide guidelines for replication of its results in other regions.

Coordinator: **Q-PLAN**

PARTNER	SHORT NAME
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	CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS
	FBCD AS
	SUSTAINABLE INNOVATIONS EUROPE SL
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